

Augmenting 19th Century Thermoelectric Greenhouse Theory with 20th Century Quantum Mechanics Raman Spectroscopy: Towards a Coherent Radiation Theory of the Atmosphere

Blair D. Macdonald

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Abstract

Current greenhouse theory is incomplete: it does not include Raman spectroscopy. It is incorrectly based on the special group of 'Tyndall' greenhouse gases, which are, by this investigation, the thermoelectric (TE-IR) gases, as detected only by thermoelectric transducers. Its premise, 'the non-GHGs Nitrogen and Oxygen do not absorb or emit infrared radiation,' presents a paradox; it contradicts both quantum mechanics and thermodynamics, where all matter above absolute 0⁰ Kelvin radiates IR photons. These (above) molecules possess quantum predicted emission spectra within the IR range of the EMS – at 2338cm⁻¹ and 1556cm⁻¹ respectively – but are only observed, and temperatures from them measured, by Raman Spectrometers, 'IR spectrometers' complement instrument. This was investigated using quantum and thermoelectric theory and their applications. A report of Raman spectrometer measurements on jet engine outlet temperatures and gas concentrations was referring to, and the following conclusions made: 1) all Raman modes (the non-GHGs) are temperature/radiation equivalent to 'IR-active modes with respect to – and complying with – the Boltzmann and Planck's constant, and quantum spectroscopy theory; 2) in support, H₂O's 3659cm⁻¹ mode is both TE-IR and Raman equivalent – supporting the 'equipartition' principle; and CO₂'s temperature can be measured by both instruments independently through its shared modes; 3) the special (1%) greenhouse gases, discovered by Tyndall in ca. 1859, are really the thermoelectric gases, detected only by receiving (non-radiating) thermo-electric transducers; 4) 'IR' spectroscopy is also based on these thermoelectric transducers, and as a consequence 'IR' spectrographs show only the spectra modes with electric dipoles and not Raman; 5) N₂, when radiated at its 2338cm⁻¹ mode, is (long lasting) metastable, and is essential to the operation of a CO₂ Laser: from this mechanism, it was concluded – contrary to current greenhouse theory – atmospheric CO₂ is heated by the exact mechanism; 6) all the atmosphere absorbs heat directly from the Sun – just as with the oceanic euphotic layer.

Key Words: greenhouse gases, John Tyndall, climate change, Raman Spectroscopy, thermoelectrics, Seebeck effect, emission spectroscopy

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1 Introduction

The current 'standard' model of greenhouse (GH) theory – developed in the 19th century, before the advent of 20th-century quantum mechanics – claims that the entire thermal-radiation behaviour of the atmosphere is explained by 1-2% of its dry constituent gases. These special greenhouse gases (GHGs), as they are termed, explain all past, present, and future climate change. These 1% GHG's – of which Methane (CH₄) is 1.7 parts in a million volume – are assumed to be the only gases to absorb 'outgoing long-wave' infrared (IR) radiation, which has been in turn re-radiated back (up) from the Earth's surface after been absorbed by the sun – by 'insolation'. Radiation heat is not directly absorbed by the sun in the atmosphere itself [1],[2]. The model also assumes, and is dependent on the premise, that the non-GHG's nitrogen (N₂) and oxygen (O₂), which comprise 99% of the dry atmosphere, do not absorb or emit IR radiation at any temperature; if they did, the model would collapse.

1.1 An IR Catastrophe

While the science may be 'settled', as it is said to be, it appears that the physics is not. Apart from being unintuitive, 'the air not absorbing the sun's energy directly', the above (non-GHG) assumption presents a paradox, a catastrophe – an IR catastrophe – as it contradicts many key principles of physics, namely it quantum mechanics and thermodynamics where all matter by above the temperature of absolute zero Kelvin is assumed to radiate electromagnetic heat-energy in the IR range of the electromagnetic spectrum (EMS). Either the physics of quantum mechanics is wrong, or GH theory is incorrect?

1.1.1 Principles of the Laws Central to Radiation Theory

Before setting a hypothesis, I would like to list the exact physics at stake. Atmospheric molecules – whether or not GHGs – must concur with the following accepted Principles, the laws central to radiation theory:

1.1.1.1 Spectroscopy:

*“The study of the interaction between electromagnetic radiation ($h\nu$) and matter is called spectroscopy; where radiation is emission or transmission of energy in the form of waves or particles through space or through a material medium. Interaction takes place by absorption and by emission, and is explained by quantum mechanics. **Emission spectroscopy** is a spectroscopic technique which examines the wavelengths of photons emitted by atoms or molecules during their transition from an excited state to a lower energy state. Each element emits a characteristic set of **discrete wavelengths** according to its electronic structure, and by observing these wavelengths the elemental composition of the sample can be determined. Emission spectroscopy developed in the late 19th century and efforts in theoretical explanation of atomic emission spectra eventually led to quantum mechanics.”*

1.1.1.2 Quantum Mechanics Schrödinger Equation

From quantum mechanics – the fundamental physics theory that describes nature on the smallest scales, involving the energy levels of atoms and subatomic particles – this equation, the Schrödinger equation, is used to calculate the predicted vibrational modes or absorption-emission spectra of atoms and molecules.

1.1.1.3 Planck’s Law

*“**Planck’s law** describes the spectral density of electromagnetic radiation emitted by a black body in thermal equilibrium at a given temperature T .”*

1.1.1.4 Boltzmann Constant

The Boltzmann constant is a fundamental constant of the universe, which links the kinetic energy and movement of molecules in a gas with temperature. By the Boltzmann constant, the observation of these and all vibrational modes at the said predicted frequencies, and their respective temperature measurement thereof, implies these modes are moving and thus are radiating IR.

1.1.1.5 The Stefan-Boltzmann Law

The Stefan-Boltzmann law is a central pillar of radiation theory, and states the following:

“All objects emit radiation if their temperature is greater than absolute zero. Absolute zero is equal to zero Kelvin, which is equal to -273°C or -460°F . An object that absorbs and emits all possible radiation at 100 percent efficiency is called a blackbody.

The Stefan-Boltzmann law, a fundamental law of physics, explains the relationship between an object’s temperature and the amount of radiation that it emits. This law (expressed mathematically as $E = \sigma T^4$) states that all objects with temperatures above absolute zero (0K or -273°C or -459°F) emit radiation at a rate proportional to the fourth power of their absolute temperature. E represents the maximum rate of radiation (often referred to as energy flux) emitted by each square meter of the object’s surface. The Greek letter “ σ ” (sigma) represents the Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($5.67 \times 10^{-8}\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}^4$); and T is the object’s surface temperature in Kelvin. The W refers to watt, which is the unit used to express power (expressed in joules per second).” [3]

1.1.1.6 Kirchhoff's Law of thermal radiation

For an arbitrary body emitting and absorbing thermal radiation in thermodynamic equilibrium, the emissivity is equal to the absorptivity—good emitter; good absorber.

1.1.1.7 Specific Heat

Notwithstanding the above, N₂ and O₂ both also have nominal, similar to other gases, heat capacities. This energy is only further transferred using convection and conduction mixing; and this presents another paradox: if most of the air does not transfer heat by radiation, and only by conduction and convection, how is this accomplished when the air is a known as a poor thermal conductor of heat-energy, and is, in fact, a thermal insulator, with a thermal conduction value of near zero: 0.024 W/m K) [4]. How can conduction and related convection stand alone as the means of heat transfer in the atmosphere? Without radiation and conduction, the atmosphere would not exist the way it does. The reality is that the atmosphere seems to behave in total accordance with the 0th and 1st laws of thermodynamics, as well as the Stefan-Boltzmann Law of radiation.

1.2 Deriving the Original GHGs

Before setting a hypothesis, the development of our understanding of the GHGs must be presented. The GH atmosphere is derived solely from detectors first developed during the early 19th Century: the thermo-electric (TE) thermo-pile transducer. This fact provides insight into and an explanation of the problem. The modern derivatives of these TE transducers are used in thermal imaging cameras and IR spectrometers, and all share a commonality: they convert thermal energy into electromotive force (emf) via the Seebeck effect. In 1859, John Tyndall used the thermopile to analyse and derive what he thought were, and what are still today believed to be, the 'greenhouse gases' – as first posited by Joseph Fourier – of the atmosphere.

1.3 Atmospheric Thermoelectric and Raman IR Spectra Lines

Table 1 shows the thermoelectric-IR modes and the Raman modes of the atmospheric gases derived solely from the radiation physics listed above (1.1.1). The outstanding issue from this table, and the central issue to this paper, is that the listed Raman Modes or Spectra (also shown on the spectrogram figure 1), are not considered to behave as so-called 'IR-active' modes in that they do not radiate or emit IR radiation – thus further contravening with the above principles of physics. These are the Raman modes of N₂'s **2338cm⁻¹**, O₂'s **1556 cm⁻¹**, CO₂'s **1338 cm⁻¹**, H₂O's **3659 cm⁻¹** and CH₄'s two **2914 cm⁻¹** and **1303 cm⁻¹**.

Table 1. Atmospheric Gases with their Respective IR Range Vibrational Modes

Molecule	Vibration Mode or Band: wavenumber (frequency)	Thermoelectric (TE) and Raman Properties	Mode Type
H ₂ O	3652 cm ⁻¹ (2.74μm)	TE (IR) and Raman	Symmetric
	1595 cm ⁻¹ (6.25μm)	TE (IR)	Asymmetric
	3756 cm ⁻¹ (2.66μm)	TE (IR)	Asymmetric
CO ₂	1388 cm ⁻¹ (7.2μm)	Non-TE (Non IR); Raman	Symmetric

	2349 cm ⁻¹ (4.257μm)	TE (IR)	Asymmetric
	667 cm ⁻¹ (14.992μm)	TE (IR)	Asymmetric
CH ₄	3020cm ⁻¹ (3.312μm)	TE (IR)	Asymmetric
	2914cm ⁻¹ (3.431μm)	Non-TE (Non-IR); Raman	Symmetric
	1508cm ⁻¹ (6.5μm)	TE (IR)	Asymmetric
	1303cm ⁻¹ (7.7μm)	Non-TE (Non-IR); Raman	Symmetric
N ₂	2338 cm ⁻¹ (4.2μm)	Non-TE (Non IR); Raman Active	Symmetric
O ₂	1556 cm ⁻¹ (6.25μm)	Non-TE (Non IR); Raman Active	Symmetric

Figure 1. The Raman Atmosphere. Spectrograph of the Earth's atmospheric gases and their Raman modes. [5] Notice these frequencies (of the molecules) are not from the table above, thermoelectric, and are not symmetric.

1.4 Problems with TE-IR: The Hairdryer Gap Paradox

To illustrate the problem of TE transducers – as claimed above in 1.2 – the thermal radiation image below of an operating hairdryer emphasises and offers insight into this thermal discrimination, which leads to the (above) 'IR catastrophe'. From the thermal image, it can be seen that the hair dryer is operating as its body is at a moderate (blue) temperature and its outlet at a red to yellow (indicated) temperature.

The discrimination is revealed with the conspicuous '**gap**' (of no apparent heat) between the hot 'flow' patch, to the left of the dryer, and the (glowing) hairdryer outlet. Why does this gap show no hot air coming directly out at the outlet, when there appears to be a hot

flow after? In principle, the hairdryer operates by radiation from its radiating electrical elements. These elements should radiate the air, and the air should, by quantum mechanics, absorb this energy.

Hair dryer creates IR
(Picture courtesy of NASA)

Figure 2. The Hair Dryer 'Gap' Paradox. A thermoelectric produced thermogram of an operating hair dryer blowing hot air, at a temperature of around 60 °C, onto a surface. Why is the blown air not glowing at the temperature of the outlet and the surface? Why the 'gap'? The answer lies in understanding thermoelectric materials.

But this is not how the image is interpreted by radiation physics. It is assumed the air is heated instead by forced convection or conduction; however, it cannot be heated by conduction (the air is a thermal insulator, as stated above), and it cannot be heated by convection for the same reason. This leaves only radiation. It must be by radiation, and if this is true, where has the physics gone wrong? Why is this hot air not explained by radiation with the dryer, and – similarly – with the standard model of the atmosphere? See section 4.5.5 for an explanation of this paradox.

1.5 Thermal Measurements by Raman Spectroscopy

Returning to the hairdryer paradox described above in Figure 2, this investigation will show that the hot air temperature 'gap' can be measured by Raman instruments or a combination of Raman and IR/thermoelectric instruments.

To demonstrate pragmatically that the IR emission spectra modes of atmospheric molecules are equivalent, differing only in their respective detectors, due to whether they possess an electric property or not, no direct primary experiment was undertaken in this investigation. Instead, a report of a previously conducted Raman spectrometer application was referred to. This report is called the: FIELD TESTS OF A LASER RAMAN MEASUREMENT SYSTEM FOR AIRCRAFT ENGINE EXHAUST EMISSIONS - 1974_[6], is referred to and termed for purposes of this investigation, 'The Raman Exhaust Report' (RER).

With the RER, the hot air expelled from a jet engine was analysed by Raman laser instruments and compared to TE/IR measurements. Essentially, it is a scaled-up version of the hairdryer; only the TE GHGs are included. Notably, the RER shows an instrument measuring the non-TE/GHG's with improved accuracy. The rationale being: if Raman

devices are good enough for practical applications like jet engines, they should be good enough for the entire atmosphere.

Below is a FLIR thermal image of an operational jet engine produced by TE transducers – the same technology as used to derive the GHGs. The bright white-hot plum image suggests – correctly – hot GHGs are expelled; what is missing, again, just as with the hairdryer paradox (above), is the ‘hot’ N₂ and O₂. In the case of this FLIR image, the plum can only be bright because of the presence of TE GHG molecules – CO₂, H₂O and the like. What result would we achieve if Raman were used to measure all the gas temperatures?

Figure 3. FLIR Image of an operating jet engine [7]. The bright ‘hot’ plum only corresponds to the GHGs within it.

The operation of this Raman device (the RER) should correspond to our understanding of quantum mechanics and thermodynamics, in that it will measure the predicted vibrational modes of each molecule it can, and also measure the corresponding temperature/energy.

Finally, the RER application should raise questions at the fundamentals of physics: if N₂ and O₂ do radiate, how is this so, given that GH theory assumes they do not? How have they become so hot so quickly from collision (conduction) alone, when they are taken, they do not absorb any IR heat energy. The simple answer, and truth, is they do emit and radiate perfectly.

1.6 Hypothesis

Without evoking any of the arguments posited in the current debate surrounding the ‘great’ political climate and GH theory, this paper aims to address the problem by examining the ‘first principles’ of physics (1.1.1). The paper highlights the problem as our ‘primitive’ use and misunderstanding of radiation in atmospheric sciences, specifically modern quantum mechanics and the Laser instruments derived from it, and particularly how it is used to form the foundational premise of the standard model of GH theory.

1. It was hypothesised that the non-GHGs – N₂ and O₂, and the ‘Raman’ modes of the GHGs (Table 1) – all comply with standard radiation physics (1.1.1): they radiate IR at their respective (QM predicted) emission spectra, equivalent to the IR modes. What separates the gases is whether they (mostly the diatomic) are Raman or

thermoelectric concerning their IR emission spectra. There are no special GHGs; only special instruments.

2. The non-GHG modes, unlike the 'Tyndall-GHGs' [8] They do not have an electric dipole moment due to their symmetric vibration; so they do not generate an electromagnetic force (EMF) by the thermo-electric transducers ('IR' detectors) – the identical transducers used to measure them. To measure these Raman modes, Raman laser instruments – complementary to IR-thermoelectric spectrometers – must be used. The Raman 'non-GHGs' are special in that they share a non-thermoelectric (non-TE) symmetric vibration nature. Raman spectrometers, by measuring the Raman modes, can measure temperature just as IR-thermoelectric spectrometers can – they are equivalent. With an understanding of Raman spectroscopy, these TE-IR spectrometers should not be used in isolation in atmospheric radiation theory.
3. What Tyndall discovered in ca. 1959 was the thermoelectric (TE) properties of the atmospheric gases, of which CO₂ and the other 'Tyndall Gases' are TE, and N₂ and O₂ are not. Thermoelectric transducers discriminate, by their process, all substances based on their ability to generate electricity, and especially the gases in which the Tyndall experiment demonstrated. The modern use of these TE transducers produces what are termed (incorrectly) 'IR' spectrographs. They are better termed TE-IR spectrometers. These TE-IR spectrometers do not radiate the samples as claimed, but rather graph the electromotive force (emf) difference between the sample and a reference IR-heat source. In doing so, they correctly produce the TE spectra bands ('IR' vibrational modes, Table 1) as predicted by quantum mechanics. As N₂ and O₂ are not TE, their modes are not produced, and as a consequence of this, N₂ and O₂ are assumed not to radiate IR as the other 'GHGs'. With Raman spectrometers, it is shown that N₂ and O₂ both share the same thermal properties as the current special GHGs in that they absorb and emit infrared radiation. By this, N₂ and O₂ and the other gases all directly absorb (and emit) IR radiation (using insolation) from the sun.
4. From understanding of the IR absorption-emission properties of N₂, with one absorption mode, it is further hypothesised that N₂ absorbs infrared photons by the identical process as demonstrated in its role in the CO₂ Laser. In this process, explained by quantum mechanics, N₂ is a pumping, metastable medium. It is the CO₂ molecule that the excited N₂ stimulates. From this, assuming electron discharge is equivalent to photon radiation, solar insolation, comprising IR photons, accounts for changes in air temperature. It will also account for the high temperatures reached by N₂ during a lightning strike, producing thunder, where the excitation causes the temperature of the air to increase by some five times the surface temperature of the sun, and the 27000K molecular temperature of N₂ in the thermosphere.
5. From an understanding of thermoelectric and Raman physics, the GHGs thus should be known as the thermoelectric gases (TEGs); the non-GHGs – the non-TEGs – as the Raman gases; and together they all constitute the GHGs, as first posited by Joseph Fourier in 1828.

1.6.1 Hypothesis Essentials

To prove my theory correct, it was required to show:

1. All vibration modes of all the atmospheric gases, predicted by quantum mechanics, can be observed by either thermoelectric IR spectrometers or Raman IR spectrometers. Raman Active (symmetric stretch) non-GHG's N₂ and O₂'s modes are observed at **2338 cm⁻¹** and **1556 cm⁻¹**, respectively (both within the IR range of the electromagnetic spectrum (EMS)) by Raman IR spectrometers (section 4.1);
2. Vibrational modes – with respect to measured temperature, and concentration – are equivalent, by the Principle of Equipartition of Energy (sections 4.2);
3. Raman Active modes must also demonstrate or imply radiation emission and absorption of IR photons, by Kirchhoff's and Stewarts Laws (sections 4.7.7);
4. CO₂'s only Raman active mode at **1388 cm⁻¹** must be shown to be temperature equivalent to its complementary 'IR active' modes – measured at **2349 cm⁻¹** and **667cm⁻¹** (section 4.1.2).
5. H₂O's modes (both Raman active and IR active) must show radiation (temperature) equivalence (section 4.1.3).
6. Further to 5., it was required to show N₂'s **2338 cm⁻¹** mode absorbs and emits radiation in the IR range of the EMS, in a real-life application (the CO₂ laser), directly affecting CO₂'s **2349 cm⁻¹** 'IR' mode (Section 4.7.1)
7. Further to 6., it will be required to show this phenomenon holds for photons – and not only electron discharge (section 4.7.1.5);
8. What is termed 'IR spectroscopy' only reveals the thermo-electric modes, and a gas with any one of those modes is termed a GHG. (Section 4.4);
9. All IR detectors do not radiate the sample; they are receiving thermoelectric transducers; they produce an electromotive force (EMF) and report the difference in EMF between the sample and the control heat source (section 4.3.7).

To prove this hypothesis, I shall first draw upon practical applications and respective physics theory, and then follow up with a detailed explanation of where the greenhouse theory has gone wrong. I shall also add supporting evidence where needed.

1.7 Approach and Scope of this Investigation

While this paper will evaluate Raman spectrometers for their equivalence to TE/IR spectrometers in terms of testing atmospheric gases, it will also explain where and how 'physics' has misconstrued the standard 'special' greenhouse gases. To prove the hypothesis, the Raman vibrational modes of the atmospheric gases will be evaluated for their respective IR radiative propensity. An already conducted experiment – where 'hot' air is measured using both IR/TE transducers and Raman spectrometers to determine its thermal properties – is referenced, along with applications of thermoelectric and quantum theory.

2 Methods

2.1 Raman Exhaust Report (RER)

The RER directed a high-power Nitrogen laser Raman spectrometer into the outlet flow of an operating (T-53) jet engine to measure the gas temperature and concentration. To calibrate and compare measurements made by the Raman laser, 'conventional' thermoelectric-IR spectrometers (table 1, p.25) and thermocouples were used.

The following are extracts from the report about the Raman method and could be repeated in any other gaseous context.

2.1.1 From the RER abstract:

"Laser induced Raman and fluorescent measurements were made in the exhaust of a T53-L13A gas turbine engine with a new field portable instrument devised specifically for gas turbine exhaust emission measurements. The gas turbine exhaust was analysed by conventional instruments for CO, CO₂, NO, NO₂, total hydrocarbons, smoke and temperature, and these data were used as a "calibration" standard for the evaluation of the laser Raman instrument (p. v)."

2.1.2 The Laser:

"The laser transmitter was an Avco Model C5000 pulsed nitrogen laser operating at a wavelength of 3371 Å (337.1 cm⁻¹)." (p.4)

2.1.3 Temperature Measurement

"The temperature of the T53 exhaust was measured using the N₂ Raman density method, whereby the temperature is assumed to be inversely proportional to the density of nitrogen, with a constant static pressure."

2.1.4 Setup:

The laser beam was pointed at and through the jet outlet as shown in the report's figure 28 (p. B46)

Figure 28 Schematic of Laser Raman Aircraft Engine Exhaust Emissions Measurement System

Figure 4. RER Setup. Pg. 46 [9]

"The gas analysis equipment used as a comparative standard for the laser Raman consisted of detectors similar to those specified by the SAE. They consisted of infrared detectors for CO, CO₂, and NO, a flame ionisation detector for total hydrocarbons, and a polarographic detector for NO and NO₂, as shown in the schematic of Figure 14. Thus, NO was measured by two different detectors. A list of the instruments used and their ranges is given in Table I." (P.20)

2.1.5 Temperature Measurement

Temperature measurements were made from the Raman laser unit and from conventional thermoelectric devices.

“Room temperature experiments were conducted in room air to measure for nitrogen..”

“Raman spectra at elevated temperatures were obtained from the exhaust of a propane/air burner. Figure 18 shows the measured spectrum of the nitrogen Raman band at 3658Å at a temperature of 1000 K and measured with a thermocouple in the burner exhaust.” Pg. 32 [9]

3 Results

Before revealing the direct results of the Raman Exhaust Report (RER), a brief recap of the experiment's purpose is necessary: I was testing the non-GHGs – N₂ and O₂'s 2338 cm⁻¹ and 1556 cm⁻¹ vibrational modes – using an IR spectroscopy complementary instrument, Raman spectroscopy, for equivalence with the modes of the GHGs.

Results draw directly from the Reports comments:

3.1 Raman Gas Vibrational Modes Observation

The Raman active vibrational modes of atmospheric gases N₂, O₂ and CO₂ were observed at the predicted wave numbers as shown in Figure 5 below:

“Raman data were obtained which could be used to accurately measure the mole fractions of the major species in the flow, i.e, N₂, O₂, and CO₂ over the entire range of engine operation conditions from idle to full power. These Raman measurements were compared with the expected values of the species concentrations as calculated from the measured fuel:/air ratio of the various operating conditions.” (P.2) [10]

Figure 3 Typical Raman Spectrum from Room Temperature Combustion Gases Using a 3371 Å Laser Source

Figure 5. RER Raman Atmosphere Spectra. Pg. 7 [9]

Notice that Figure 5 shows not only the wave numbers for the different gases but also their respective concentrations.

The following figures show Raman Spectra in detail:

“Initial tests were conducted in air at the AVCO Everett Laboratories to verify the predicted performance of the laser Raman field unit. Figures 18, 19, and 20 show spectra obtained in the spectral regions that correspond to vibrational transitions in N₂, NO and H₂O at 2330 cm⁻¹, 1876 cm⁻¹ and 3652 cm⁻¹ that will produce Raman lines at 3658, 3600, and 3844 Å, respectively.” Pg. 43

3.1.1 N₂ 2338cm Raman Vibrational Mode Spectra

The Raman spectra of the N₂ molecule's 2338 cm⁻¹ mode are shown below in Figure 6.

3.1.2

Figure 18 Ambient Air Nitrogen Vibrational Raman Line at 2330 cm^{-1}

Figure 6. 'Figure 18' N_2 2330 cm^{-1} Raman Spectra. Pg. 32 [10]

3.1.3 O_2 1556 cm^{-1} Vibration Mode and Concentration

O_2 was not the molecule of attention; however, the Raman spectra were observed to calculate concentration levels.

"Raman measurements were made of the O_2 concentrations in the T-53 engine exhaust. These measurements show excellent agreement when compared with the expected concentration values based on the measured fuel-to-air ratio from the operating engine. Typical data of the O_2 vibrational Raman line in the hot exhaust gases are shown in Figure 31. The system was calibrated in the field for its effective cross section and system transfer function using the O_2/N_2 ratio obtained from ambient air, assuming that air is composed of 21% O_2 and 78% N_2 on a mole basis." (P.43)

Figure 31 Typical Spectral Data of O₂ in Hot Exhaust Gases

Figure 7. O₂ 1556 cm⁻¹ Raman Spectra. Pg. 41 [10]

3.1.4 H₂O 3652 cm⁻¹ Vibrational Mode

H₂O's Raman mode was observed; its spectrum is shown in Figure 8 below.

"Water vapour detection is shown in Figure 20 (below), where a signal/noise ratio of about 100 at a relative concentration of about 1% of the atmospheric nitrogen signal is observed." (P. 31)

Figure 20 Atmospheric Water Vapor Vibrational Raman Line at 3652 cm⁻¹

Figure 8. H₂O 3652 cm⁻¹ Raman Spectra. Pg. 34 [10]

3.1.5 CO₂ 1338 cm⁻¹ Vibrational Mode (and Temperature)

Carbon dioxide's predicted 1338 cm⁻¹ mode was observed, and its spectra are shown in Figure 9 below.

"A further example of a room temperature Raman spectrum is shown in Figure 17, which is the spectrum of the CO₂ doublet at 1285 cm⁻¹ and 1388 cm⁻¹ wave numbers."

Figure 17 Experimental Raman Spectrum of Carbon Dioxide at Room Temperature

Figure 9. CO₂ 1338 Raman Spectra [9]

“Of special interest is the appearance of secondary peaks at 1265 cm⁻¹ and 1409 cm⁻¹ wave numbers which correspond to transitions from the lowest excited vibrational level of CO₂, the 010 level. This level is appreciably populated even at room temperature. Measurement of the ratio of the secondary to the primary peak is a sensitive means of temperature measurement throughout the temperature range of interest for turbine exhausts as will be shown later in this report.” [9] (P.32)

Figure 20 Experimental Raman Spectrum of Carbon Dioxide at -1000°K in a Propane/Air Burner Exhaust

Figure 10. CO2 Spectra. Pg. 33 [9]

3.2 Gas Concentrations by Raman Spectroscopy

Gas concentrations for the following atmospheric gas were measured:

3.2.1 H2O Concentrations

“The water vapor Raman data that was obtained from the exhaust of the T-53 engine is shown in the following tabulation: “

Power Setting	Raman Measurment	Calculated From F/A
(1)	(2)	(3)
7%	0.0274	0.0372
30%	0.0216	0.0416
100%	0.0226	0.0567

The Raman Measurement values in (2) are the ratios of the peak value of the water Raman signals in the 3652 cm⁻¹ band to the peak value of the nitrogen Raman signals at 2330 cm⁻¹. The system was calibrated - using the ambient air values. The calculated values used the same F/A data as was used in the above O₂ and CO₂ comparisons and included a slight correction for the ambient air water vapor.”(P.51)

3.2.2 CO2 Concentration

“The response of the laser Raman instrument to CO₂ was calibrated at the beginning of the test program with a T53 engine by using the previous conventionally measured CO₂

concentration from this engine at the 60% power setting. ... These data are displayed in Figure 33, which shows the volume percent CO₂ as a function of the percent shaft horsepower of the engine." Pg. 59 [10]

"Similar Raman measurements were made of the CO₂ concentration in the T53 turbine engine exhaust and are shown in Figure 33 (below). **The Raman data were normalized to the (IR) gas analysis data at the 60% power point.** Absolute CO₂ calibrations using the atmosphere were not conducted in the field because of the uncertainty in the CO₂ concentration of the air in the Bridgeport, Connecticut industrial area." (P.48)

Figure 33 Volume % CO₂ as Measured from Raman Scattering vs Shaft Horse Power (SHP), %

Figure 11. CO₂ Raman vs IR/thermoelectric. Raman measurements taken at 1338 cm⁻¹ match the IR thermoelectric 2349 cm⁻¹ mode. Pg.50 [10]

3.2.3 N₂/O₂ Ratio

"The ratio of the corrected O₂ to N₂ Raman signals can then be used to obtain the O₂/N₂ mole ratio. The system was calibrated in the field for effective cross section and system transfer function by using the O₂/N₂ ratio obtained from ambient air and by assuming that air is 21% O₂ and 78% N₂ on a mole basis. The results of the oxygen measurements are shown in Figure 32 where the O₂/N₂ mole ratio is calculated from the fuel/air ratio of the operating T-53 engine, using an approximate value of hydrogen/carbon mole ratio of 2.0. Perfect

agreement would cause the data to fall in the line connecting zero with the point labeled "air".

Figure 32 O₂/N₂ Mole Ratio for T-53 Engine Raman Measurement vs Calculated Value

Figure 12. N₂ O₂ Concentration Raman Measurements. Pg. 49 [10]

3.2.4 NO

"An attempt was made to detect nitric oxide (NO) in the T53 exhaust using the 1876 cm⁻¹ vibrational Raman transition. The T53 engine typically produces 100 ppm of NO when operating at full power. Because the fluorescence level in the T53 at full power was about 100 times greater than the expected signal from NO, the required integration times for detection were longer than the test time available." (p. 51)

3.3 Temperature Measurement by Raman Spectroscopy

Temperature measurements were made from Raman Active modes of the atmospheric gases, as follows:

"The temperature profiles obtained in this way (Raman) are plotted in Figure 37 and appear quite reasonable. Thermocouple measurements in the exhaust stream gave an average of 7250 K for the 7% power point and 8900 K for the 100% power point, which is in good agreement with the Raman data. **Since it is not subject to thermocouple heat loss corrections, the laser Raman data is inherently a more reliable and accurate thermometer than a thermocouple.** Further work is required, however, to definitely establish the precision of the laser Raman method as a hot gas temperature measurement technique. (p. 54)"

3.3.1 N₂ Temperature

“Accurate temperature profiles were obtained in the T-53 exhaust using laser Raman scattering from nitrogen via the density method. The spectral analysis of “hot bands” was found to be a less accurate method in the T-53 exhaust because of the high level of laser induced fluorescence. Although the feasibility has now been demonstrated, further work is required to quantify the precision of the laser Raman method for temperature measurements in aircraft engine exhaust streams.” (Pg. 59)[10]

“The sensitivity of the method is shown in Figure 27, which is a plot of the ratio of the Raman scattering at 3634 Å to the Raman scattering at 3658 Å for pure nitrogen as a function of temperature. Over the expected range of turbine exhaust operation, i. e. 9000K to 12000 K. the uncertainty in the ratio is 9% per 100°K or about 1% per 11K temperature uncertainty—an attainable value using the (010)/(000) CO₂ Raman ratio method as.. discussed. Since the Raman intensity in the $\Delta J = -2$ side band of N₂ (with circular polarization) corresponds to about an apparent level of 1000 PPM of CO a 1% measurement of the side band intensity would enable detection and measurement of 10 PPM CO. This is difficult, requiring an S/N of 100 at low signal levels, but can in principle be done.” (P.41)[9]

Figure 27 The Computed Ratio of Nitrogen Raman Scattering ($\Delta J=2$) at $\lambda = 3624 \text{ \AA}$ to Nitrogen Raman Scattering ($\Delta J=0$) at $\lambda = 3658 \text{ \AA}$

Figure 13. N₂ Prediction to Observation. Temperature measurement of a non-GHG by Raman spectrometer at N₂'s 2330 cm⁻¹ predicted mode. Pg.43 [9]

“5. TEMPERATURE SENSITIVITY

The effects of increasing temperature become important to the laser Raman turbine exhaust analysis system in many ways. Foremost is the impact on the ratio of the peak Raman signal intensity of a particular species to the actual concentration of that species. The tacit assumption in previous work has usually been that the Raman signal is proportional to species concentration. However, over the temperature range of interest this proportionality constant is somewhat temperature dependent. "

Figure 21 Computed Nitrogen Normalization Error as a Function of Temperature for a Detector with a Resolution of 1 Å

Figure 14 N₂ Temp. Pg.34 [9]

3.3.2 Raman CO₂ Temperature

"Figure 22 shows the estimated ratio of the peak (000) CO₂ signal to the total CO₂ concentration as a function of temperature.

Figure 22 Computed Carbon Dioxide Normalization Error as a Function of Temperature for a Detector with a Resolution of 1 Å

Figure 15. CO₂ Temperature Measurement by Raman Spectrometer. Pg 35[9]

From the above, it is apparent that an independent method of temperature measurement is a desirable adjunct to a laser Raman turbine exhaust measurement system. The use of the CO₂ Raman spectrum seems to be a reasonable means to satisfy this requirement. **In particular the measurement of the ratio of the (000) CO₂ peak to the (010) CO₂ peak seems especially well suited for a temperature determination.**

Also shown in Figure 23 are two experimental points representing a room temperature determination, which agreed exactly with the theoretical curve, and a higher temperature data point obtained from the propane/air burner exhaust CO₂ spectra.

Figure 23 The Computed Temperature Dependence of the Ratio of the Raman Scattering from the 010 Level of CO₂ to the Raman Scattering from the 000 Level of CO₂. Two Experimental Points are shown.

Figure 16. CO₂ as Thermometer – by Raman Spectroscopy. Pg. 37 [9]

The disagreement of the high temperature data point with respect to theory is probably caused by a combination of noise and the positioning error of the thermocouple used to measure the temperature vs. the position of the laser focal point in the propane burner exhaust. More careful experiments to verify this theoretical curve and/or to calibrate the functional relationship of $N(010)/N(000)$ vs temperature should be conducted. " [9](P.32)

3.4 RER Conclusion

The following is the conclusion to the Raman exhaust report:

1. *Excellent agreement of (Raman) O₂ and CO₂ measurements with conventional exhaust gas measurements and correlations with engine fuel-air ratio.*
2. *Excellent agreement with smoke number measurements, with a calibration at one point only.*
3. *Good agreement of temperature profile measurements with thermocouple data.*
4. *Total hydrocarbons were detected and compared to flame ionization measurements to within a factor of +2 over a range of three decades of concentration.*
5. *Water vapor has been detected in exhausts under all conditions. Calibration requires fundamental water cross-section data as a function of temperature, which is not now available. "*

4 Discussions

While this section will focus directly on the above RER experiment results, it will, using principles and applications known in physics, also broaden to address the implications of this work on thermoelectric and Raman spectroscopy applications and theory, as well as our general understanding of climate and related areas. It will also bring in applications of Raman and thermoelectric devices, as well as applications of atomic radiation theory, all in support of this paper's hypothesis. This is a complicated issue to put into order; my best attempt was made.

More references and background to Raman Spectroscopy can be found in the Appendix from 8.2.

4.1 Quantum - Schrödinger equation - Predicted and Raman Observed Vibration Modes

The RER observes and applies the predicted vibrational modes viewed in Table 1.

“infrared and Raman spectra: the interaction of the molecule with electromagnetic radiation. The interaction of the electric vector of the electromagnetic radiation with the molecule will give rise to infrared absorption and inelastic scattering (Raman) spectra...” pg. 12 [11]

4.1.1 N₂ and O₂

These modes - particularly N₂ and O₂ - are predicted by the Schrödinger equation, the centrepiece of modern atomic physics. This prediction is consistent with standard quantum mechanics and the understanding of emission spectra. This equation predicts the atomic vibrational mode frequencies for all matter, including the atmospheric gases. N₂ and O₂'s predicted modes are observed at the frequencies **2360 cm⁻¹** and **1580cm⁻¹**, respectively - well within the infrared band of the electromagnetic spectrum, [12]. These modes are identified in the context of temperature, and many papers reveal these predicted vibration functions[13], [14],[15]. Table 2 (below) is one example and shows the predicted wavenumber where ω_e (column 3) of N₂ and O₂'s predicted modes at 2360 cm⁻¹ and 1580 cm⁻¹.

Table 2. Table of predicted N₂ and O₂ vibration modes derived from the Schrodinger equation [12].

The third column from the left shows the vibration mode wavenumbers. Note H₂ is predicted (and also observed by Raman).

Molecular Data and Statistical Weights of the J Levels for some Linear Molecules ^a								
Molecule	Molecular data					Nuclear spin	Statistical weight (g_n)	
	B_e (cm ⁻¹)	ω_e (cm ⁻¹)	$\omega_e x_e$ (cm ⁻¹)	α_e (cm ⁻¹)	r_e (Å)		J (even)	J (odd)
¹ H ₂	60.80	4395	117	2.99	0.742	¹ / ₂	1	3
² H ₂	30.43	3118	64.1	1.05	0.742	1	6	3
¹⁴ N ₂	2.010	2360	14.46	0.0187	1.094	1	6	3
¹⁶ O ₂	1.446	1580	12.07	0.0158	1.207	0	0	1
¹⁹ F ₂	0.86	892	1.435	¹ / ₂	1	3
³⁵ Cl ₂	0.2438	565	4.0	0.0017	1.988	³ / ₂	6	10
¹² C ¹⁶ O	1.931	2170	13.46	0.0175	1.128	...	1	1
¹ H ³⁵ Cl	10.59	2990	52.05	0.302	1.275	...	1	1
¹² C ¹⁶ O ₂ ^b	0.3906 ($B_0 = 0.3895$)				1.162 ($r_0 = 1.163$) 1.202 (CC) ($r_0 = 1.207$) 1.059 (CH) ($r_0 = 1.059$)	0	1	0
¹² C ₂ ¹ H ₂ ^b	1.1838 ($B_0 = 1.1769$)					¹ / ₂	1	3

^a Reference (1).
^b Reference (6).

GH theory ignores these modes of the diatomic molecules, and the 'Raman active' modes within the so-called GH gases (CO₂'s 1338 cm⁻¹ and CH₄'s 2914 cm⁻¹ and 1303 cm⁻¹). Raman spectroscopy confirms that these modes are real, and we will soon learn that they correspond to the theory of IR radiation.

4.1.2 CO₂'s 1338 cm⁻¹ and the Principle of Equipartition

CO₂'s third QM predicted vibration mode or vibrational spectra – the mode not included in GH theory – is observed at 1338 cm⁻¹ by the RER in the IR of the EMS: only with Raman spectrometers. This mode is not observed with IR thermoelectric detectors as it does not have an electric dipole moment and thus does not generate an electromotive force – more on this in a following section. By the Principle of Equipartition[16], this Raman vibrational mode should be emission equivalent to the TE/IR (GHG) modes and assumed so. If it were not for Raman spectroscopy, this mode would only be predicted and not observed. That there is a mode implies there is vibration, and through the Boltzmann constant, this vibration implies a temperature equivalent IR emission and absorption proportional to the vibrational energy of the mode, as all spectra lines do.

4.1.2.1 The Significance of Equipartition to Degrees of Freedom and Normal Modes

*"In classical statistical mechanics, the equipartition theorem relates the temperature of a system to its average energies. The original idea of equipartition was that, in thermal equilibrium, energy is shared equally among all of its various forms; for example, the average kinetic energy per **degree of freedom** in translational motion of a molecule should equal that in rotational motion.[16]"*

Normal modes (IR spectra bands) are derived from how many degrees of freedom a molecule has; and it says they are equal in their output. So it is significant; they are equal in terms of heat-energy radiation.

4.1.3 H₂O's 3652 cm⁻¹: IR/TE and Raman Modes Equivalent

The Raman observation of H₂O's 3652 cm⁻¹ vibrational mode is significant as this mode is both TE- 'IR active' (as shown in figure 17 below) and Raman active; it is a 'dual' Raman-TE mode. This mode is an absolute demonstration, observation, and the practical application, via the Principle of Equipartition, that these modes are equivalent. This also shows the detectors are equivalent. What is separating our understanding of the modes will be addressed when we look at how the IR modes are derived. This discovery has massive ramifications on the outcome of this investigations conclusion, and radiation physics as a whole – water has a dual means of absorption and emission.

Figure 17. H₂O IR (thermoelectric) Vibration Modes and Respective Spectrum. Notice the 3652cm⁻¹ is clearly shown to be IR. [17]

4.1.3.1 Contravention of the Rule of Mutual Exclusion

It appears the above H₂O 3652 cm⁻¹ mode is a contravention of the rule of mutual exclusion, where “no normal modes can be both Infrared and Raman active in a molecule that possesses a centre of symmetry”. However, H₂O is a special exception as described below.

“The fact that H₂O does not obey the rule of mutual exclusion indicates that the H₂O molecule is not centrosymmetric (it is bent). As expected, the ν₁ symmetric stretch is also strongly Raman active.

Band H ₂ O	Infrared	Raman
-----------------------	----------	-------

v1 - symmetric stretching (3652cm ⁻¹)	strong	strong
v2 - asymmetric stretching (3755cm ⁻¹)	very strong	weak
v3 - bending (1595cm ⁻¹)	very strong	weak

(Source, online lecture notes).

Does this mean H₂O offers the best example and application of the law of equipartition? Explanation is beyond the scope of this investigation.

4.1.3.2 Solar IR Insolation Radiation Heats Water

In the euphotic zone of water bodies: “almost all of the (IR) radiation is absorbed converting electromagnetic energy into heat. Most of this absorption is carried out by water molecules with the first 50 metres”. Pg. 38 [18] From this, it can be deduced that the air (‘the ocean of if) absorbs IR photons just as an ocean of water does. The question is, why is this principle not so for the atmospheric gases? The answer is, as claimed here, the air does absorb with its Raman and TE modes.

4.2 Temperature Measurement – by Raman

IR thermoelectric detectors cannot measure the temperature of N₂ or O₂ above absolute zero Kelvin, but here, Raman spectroscopy can not only detect the modes, but also measure the temperature of the molecule from the intensity or kinetic energy of the mode signal.

4.2.1 Raman Spectroscopy and the Raman Effect – No Confusion

For clarification purposes, using the word ‘Raman’ does not imply a Raman effect mechanism leading to thermal heating of the atmosphere. Pre-publishing reviewers made claims to this effect. To counter this, this paper claims that Raman Spectrometers identify the predicted molecular vibrational modes of the ‘non-GHGs’ in the IR range of the EMS, as well as the different parameters measured, such as temperature. Raman spectrometers exploit the Raman effect with their lasers. The vibrational modes of the atmosphere are described and predicted by QM and are observed by Raman Spectroscopy.

4.2.2 Temperature Detector Equivalence

From the Raman RER experiment, it is demonstrated that the two detectors used within the IR range of the EMS, Raman and thermoelectric, are equivalent in terms of the vibrational and temperature behaviour of the molecule. H₂O’s 3659 cm⁻¹ mode is equivalent (as in the above section 4.1), thus the detectors’ IR and Raman are equivalent. What is more, the temperature was measured from CO₂’s Raman active 1338 cm⁻¹ mode alone (3.3.2); and this value compared well and calibrated ‘favourably’ by Raman’s complementary instrument, the thermoelectric IR detector – figure 17 above. From this, it can be implied that all modes and thus molecules are equivalent; they are only separated or discriminated by the detector ‘observing’ them. The RER demonstrates that temperature measurements of all atmospheric gases can be made reliably and accurately from the Raman vibrational modes alone; the Raman detector, on its own, could measure and quantify the ‘special GHGs’ (thermoelectric gases). As evidence of this, Raman instruments are used as an instrument of choice on solar system space probes– more on this in a following section.

From the above equivalences, we can say a GH atmosphere without this Raman vibrational mode knowledge is incomplete: these Raman temperature observations are not – as it stands today – used or discussed in GH theory and they should.

4.2.3 Raman Temperature Measurements and the Boltzmann Constant

By the Boltzmann constant, the observation of these and all vibrational modes at the said predicted frequencies, and their respective temperature measurement thereof, implies these modes are moving and thus are radiating IR. By observation, from this experiment, these modes are radiating – IR heat – consistent with thermodynamics and quantum mechanics; if they were not there would be a contradiction.

4.2.4 Raman Measurements and the Stefan Boltzmann Law

As both N₂ and O₂ – independently – show a temperature value, as measured by Raman laser detectors, they must be said to be radiating in accordance to the Stefan-Boltzmann law. The Stefan-Boltzmann law is a central pillar to radiation theory, and states the following: expressed mathematically as $E = \sigma T^4$.

This Raman signal is in total contrast to current GH theory – where it is not allowed. This misconception can only be due to the Raman detectors measuring the N₂ and O₂, and the TE/IR detectors not measuring it. This finding has direct significance to blackbody radiation theory and suggests it is incomplete, requiring updating with respect to the Raman observations made here, and everywhere in the fields of modern chemistry and physics.

4.2.5 N₂ and O₂ and Planck's Law

The above claim also pertains to Planck's Law. Planck's law – with the addition of the Raman-IR modes, suggesting they are 'blackbody' emitters – will require amending.

4.3 Thermoelectrics: Deriving the 'Standard' GHGs

From the Raman Exhaust Experiment we can deduce all the modes of atmospheric molecules emit and absorb IR radiation by quantum mechanics – they are all GHGs. We now need to explain how it is that we have come to believe in a special, select set of 'GHGs' derived by TE/IR alone, totally ignoring the quantum mechanics-predicted and observed Raman modes. This section of the discussion directly addresses this question.

To illustrate the role that thermoelectric transducers have played in GH theory, I will first demonstrate their direct involvement in the 1859 GH experiment and then explain how thermopiles function. This will be followed by an analysis of the current modern applications of this technology, including non-contact IR thermometers and thermal imaging cameras. I will conclude this section by connecting thermoelectrics to infrared spectroscopy, where I will demonstrate how and where – consistent with all their properties – these spectrometers only reveal one aspect of reality: the thermoelectric electric atmosphere. In this section, I will need to show what TE/IR spectrometers produce, how they produce, and importantly, what they do not make – and explain why not. I need to show they are inadmissible (as they are currently used) as an instrument if used on their own, and without their known complement – Raman spectrometers. By the end of this section, we shall understand they are best-termed TE-IR spectrometers – as hypothesised – from the fact their thermoelectric measurements purely produce their output.

4.3.1 Historical Order of IR Spectroscopy

Before we begin, let's take a quick look at the order and history of discoveries and claims; it reveals a great deal on its own. The developmental history of IR-thermo-electric spectroscopy, and as a direct consequence, the GHGs is all 19th Century, pre-quantum mechanics knowledge; the Raman active–non–GH gases–modes are all the domain of the 20th Century quantum mechanics, and are indeed on their own identified only by quantum technology, lasers.

It should be made clear that this investigation should not undo the merits of TE-IR spectroscopy per se; it rightly reveals part of the IR atmosphere. Science should have been searching for the other 'part' and questioning the extrapolation made from its incompleteness. Additionally, it is worth noting that Tyndall (and others) did not understand why these gases were special; it would take quantum mechanics to explain this, which was yet to be discovered in the mid-19th century.

The operation of the thermopile will be covered in the next section.

4.3.2 The Tyndall Experiment: the Thermo-electric, Transducer Derived GH Atmosphere

In 1859, John Tyndall [19],[20] published his analysis of the atmospheric gases using the newly developed thermopile transducer and galvanometer [21],[22],[23],[24],[25]. Prior to this experiment, the entire atmosphere was thought to consist of, as posited by Joseph Fourier in 1828, only 'heat trapping' gases, all acting as a 'greenhouse' and insulating the Earth. Tyndall redefined this group of all gases to consist of a 'small' group of special gases that, specifically, by his experiment, absorb and emit infrared [26] Thermal radiation.

Below (figure 18) is the setup of Tyndall's experiment: he isolated all the atmospheric gases between a heat source and a thermopile. He analysed them for their change in electric flow, measured by the galvanometer.

Figure 18. Tyndall's 1859 Setup For Measuring Radiant Heat Absorption By Gases. The apparatus clearly shows a thermopile, a galvanometer and a heat source. [21]

Tyndall noted – from the gases that moved the galvanometer – N₂ and O₂ did not appear to be affected by the heat source, while others, including H₂O, CO₂, CH₄, NO₂, and O₃, did. He concluded that the latter group of gases absorbed the thermal radiation, while the former did not. From this, the latter group is today known as the GHGs, and the retired – N₂ and O₂ – as the non-GHGs, and these non-GHGs were thus assumed to be transparent to thermal radiation.

This discovery – on its own – sounds convincing and plausible, even special; but with knowledge of thermopiles, thermoelectrics and the Seebeck effect – not to mention modern quantum mechanics and the (above) Raman instruments – it is not.

4.3.2.1 Tyndall IR Thermoelectric Misconception

To reiterate – based on the following facts about thermoelectrics – I claim what John Tyndall really discovered, by the thermopile transducer, are not the ‘special’ heat-trapping gases but rather only the thermoelectric gases of the atmosphere (TE) – the gases that generate electricity via the Seebeck effect and TE transducers. Suppose we were to generate electricity with a thermoelectric pile transducer from hot gases, which we could, we would source the same apparatus as Tyndall’s experiment above. However, while it is possible to generate electricity from these select gases, the amount produced is so small that it is uneconomic; if this were not the case, we’d be doing it—more on this in the coming sections.

4.3.2.2 Unrecognised Seebeck effect in MS Word

It should be pointed out before going further: the mere typing of the words ‘thermoelectrics’ and ‘Seebeck’ triggers the spellcheck of my MS Word word-processor, suggesting this knowledge is not at all disseminated as other sciences. Similarly, few – if any – modern general science textbooks (for university and school) cover the topic of thermoelectrics; it was from physics online that the knowledge for this investigation was found.

4.3.3 TE (Thermoelectric)/ IR Spectroscopy

The next set of instruments in the thermoelectric transducer family that also exploits thermoelectrics, and misinterprets what they detect, are termed ‘IR spectrometers’. They are at the centre of the field of what is termed incorrectly ‘IR spectroscopy’; they are more correctly termed TE (Thermoelectric)/ IR Spectroscopy. They are the modern instruments that define the said special GH gases, and without this assumption, all the gases would be assumed to trap heat, just as posited by Joseph Fourier in the early 19th Century.

TE/IR spectrometers are the modern version of the Tyndall experiment – and they (I claim) share the same flaws as the Tyndall experiment, in that they discriminate on N₂ and O₂. They – whatever the thermoelectric detector method – share the same properties or problems as the TE/IR cameras and TE/IR thermometers, as well as CO₂ sensors: they do not measure all matter, but rather discriminate against what is not thermoelectric. They imply these gases do not interact with ‘light’, and thus are not greenhouse gases. As this must be wrong – if not impossible – understanding TE/IR spectrometers will help us know where we have gone wrong in forming this paradox.

One truth about them is they are incorrectly thought to be the only proof of how radiating light, in the form of infrared electromagnetic photons from the Sun, interacts with matter, and in particular, for this investigation, the atmospheric gases..

4.3.3.1 TE/IR Spectrographs

TE/IR spectrometers measure or record the entire infrared range of the electromagnetic spectrum, frequency by frequency, by comparing a sample to a reference heat source. They reveal – as can be seen in the spectrograph below (figure 19) – the quantum mechanics predicted vibrational modes or emission spectra that possess ‘asymmetric electric dipole moments’ such as (there are others): H₂O’s **3652 cm⁻¹** (2.74μm), **1595 cm⁻¹** (6.25μm), and **3756 cm⁻¹** (2.66μm); CO₂’s **2349 cm⁻¹** (4.257μm), and **667 cm⁻¹** (14.992μm); CH₄’s **3020cm⁻¹** (3.312μm), **1508cm⁻¹** (6.5μm), and O₃’s **1103 cm⁻¹**, **701 cm⁻¹**, and **1042 cm⁻¹**.

Figure 19. Infrared Spectrograph of the atmosphere [27]. This spectrogram does not account for Raman modes and thermoelectric principles. See 4.4.4 for a correct interpretation of this spectrograph.

4.3.4 The IR Dipole Misconception

Here is the crux of the problem. The above modes all have one thing in common: defining them as ‘IR active’ and part of a GHG molecule, and that is, they all have asymmetric modes with ‘**electric dipole**’ movements. Standard GH theory definitions clearly state this; however, when it is understood that the thermoelectric transducers receive these ‘thermal’ - ‘electric’ signals, only from these modes, just like a radio receives electromagnetic ‘radio’ signals, common sense prevails. Those modes that do not have electric dipole moments are not received and are incorrectly interpreted as non-thermal/non-GHG. The following highlights this current understanding:

Diatomic molecules are observed in the Raman spectra but not in the IR spectra. This is because diatomic molecules have one band and no permanent (electric) dipole, and therefore one single vibration. An example of this would be O₂ or N₂. [15]

For some reason, the ‘electric’ in these ‘electric dipoles’ definition is interpreted to explain the thermal in the ‘GH’ atmosphere, and this is wrong. Of course, if we want to observe these non-TE modes, a Raman Laser is the solution.

In Section 4.5.4 below, I describe how the spectrograph is actually produced.

4.3.5 TE/IR – Transducing – Spectrometer Configuration

To demonstrate that dispersive TE/IR spectrometers operate on the same principle as the CO₂ sensor (explained below) and the Tyndall experiment setup, and only measure

electricity production from the radiated heat, we need to examine the component parts of the instrument and deduce how it works. The following schematics (figures 20 and 21) show the working of a typical dispersive IR spectrometer [28] And the Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometer. I shall demonstrate both these share the same principles: transducer detectors, heat source, separate sample and empty reference/control tubes or cells; but differ in that they have a ‘splitter’ that can split and read output from a specific band of the electromagnetic spectrum, and by this create a graph – a spectrograph – as shown above.

4.3.5.1 The dispersive IR Spectrometer:

Figure 20. Operations Schematic of Dispersive Spectrometer [29], [28]. Notice the splitter and the division from the reference (control) and the sample.

Just as with the CO₂ sensor, the IR (heat) source of the dispersive ‘IR spectrometer’ is heated to a considerable temperature – some 1500 °C (3:40 [30] – With this high temperature, the relatively low temperature of the sample will stand out. Also, note that glass is not used to prepare samples; instead, sodium chloride (NaCl) salt plates or Potassium Bromide (KBr) plates are used. These slides or plates are said to be transparent to IR radiation, but this is not so, and is misleading; they are non-thermoelectric, or are at least, less so.

4.3.5.2 The Fourier Transform IR (FTIR) spectrometer

The FTIR has a different configuration, but the main features remain: a ‘sample compartment’, a ‘source’ (heat source), and a ‘detector’.

Figure 21. Operations Schematic of Fourier Transform IR (FTIR) spectrometer [29].

4.3.6 All 'IR Spectrometers' Detectors are Thermoelectric (TE/IR) Transducers

It can be shown, contrary to standard belief, all 'IR spectrometers' [31] use thermoelectric transducers[32] [33].

*"Thermo detectors mainly classified into: (1) **thermopile** detectors that change in electromotive force, (2) **bolometers** that that change resistance, (3) **pyroelectric** detectors that change in dielectric surface charge, (4) **diodes** that change in voltage."* Pg 2 [34]

With the likes of, for example, Mercury Cadmium Telluride (**MCT**) spectrometers, it can (also) be inferred, by the similarity of their respective output, they too are TE detectors. All show the same results and do not detect non-thermoelectric vibration modes of N₂, O₂, CO₂, CH₄, and others. They also do not fully detect solid Germanium or CL₂. This includes Golay cells, where they are included as transducers – slide 16 [35].

The photodiodes are used as detectors of UV light, as presented on a spectrograph. The detector differs from the thermopile in that, to the best of our knowledge, it does not discriminate between molecules, unlike the thermopile. Evidence of this is in how samples can be in glass and plastic [36]This is not possible for IR spectroscopy, as explained.

A final note to this section: all spectrometers are named after what band of the electromagnetic spectrum is radiated in – microwave, UV and so on – IR is also called for the same reason. The problem arises when it is understood that there are two methods of detecting all the samples' vibrational bands, Raman and thermoelectric. For this reason, I suggest the names TE/IR and Raman IR.

4.3.7 The Misconception and Fallacy of 'IR Spectrometers' Radiating the Sample

'IR/TE spectrometers' – and all other 'IR' technology - share the standard assumption the sample gases are radiated with IR light (heat), and as a result the – what is termed – an 'IR spectrograph' (shown) is produced revealing the said (above) corresponding absorption/emission spectra at the said modes; and hence, because of the thermal radiation, we have the name 'IR spectroscopy'. This assumption is most likely inferred from the following standard definition of spectroscopy, pointing to it being a study of light (photons) radiating a sample:

*"Absorption spectroscopy refers to **spectroscopic** techniques that measure the **absorption** of radiation, as a function of frequency or wavelength, due to its interaction with a sample. The sample absorbs energy, i.e., photons, from the radiating field."*[37]

Samples may be radiated for the many types of spectrometers: gamma, X-ray, UV, visible, and microwave; however, for 'IR' is not so, as we shall now investigate.

4.4 The Thermo-electric 'Detectors': How Transducers Function

To develop our knowledge further, we need first to understand how the Tyndall GH deriving apparatus works and how they are connected to modern knowledge and instruments. In the case of GH theory and other so-called IR radiation areas, it is not deduced correctly: thermopiles and the like transduce an IR heat signal into electricity – hence the term 'thermo-electrics' in the context of infrared. But, as we shall see in this section, just as with the TE-IR spectrographs, they do not transduce everything.

4.4.1 The Seebeck Effect, the Thermocouple and the Thermopile [38]

In 1821, Thomas Seebeck [39] Discovered electricity current was produced when two metals – of different kinds – are joined at one end and were exposed to 'hot objects'. He found what is known as the thermocouple [40]): with a device to measure the electric current – or electromotive force (EMF) – the electric current produced was found proportional to the IR Temperature (T) as given by the following equation

$$E_{EMF} = -S\Delta T \quad (1)$$

Where the S is the Seebeck coefficient (also known as thermopower). This discovery is said to be one of the most significant breakthroughs in the history of science and engineering: we were able to accurately measure temperature for the first time.

Thermopiles consist of multiple thermocouples connected in series (Figure 22).

Figure 22 Thermopiles. Above, a schematic of a thermopile [41] Below, The Modern thermopile. [42]

4.4.2 The Thermopile: A Heat to Electricity Transducer

The thermopile is a transducer: it converts one form of energy – IR radiation – into another – electricity. The voltage output relationship is illustrated in the figure below: as temperature rises, the voltage output increases.

Figure 23. Thermopile Voltage Output by Temperature

4.4.3 Thermoelectric Substances

In the context of TE transducers, TE substances refer to, unlike the current reference, the substances detected; and not the substances used to detect.

Before we go deeper into the chemistry as to why some substances are TE while others are not, a vital starter: while all substances radiate IR heat – by the laws of quantum mechanics and thermal dynamics – not all substances are thermoelectric. This may seem trivial; however, in the light of modern climate science – and where it has led us – it is not. What Tyndall’s experiment revealed was only **the gases** that generate electricity via the thermopile, not the other phases of matter. Had he equally tested the solids and liquids for the same property, he would have found similar patterns amongst these.

4.4.3.1 TE Solids and Gases

While most solids are TE, only some substances – like water and ice – transduce a near-perfect electric signal to correspond with the real temperature of the substance: shiny metals, conversely, deliver a very poor signal and require a near 100% correction. This correction factor between thermoelectric transduction and the real temperature is what is termed the *emissivity* of a substance; this subject matter is open to further research as a consequence of this investigation.

4.4.3.2 Greenhouse Liquids and Solids – Water and Glass

By GH reasoning, where it is deduced – by thermoelectric transducers – the GHGs are transparent to the visible spectrum, and ‘opaque to the IR’, Water should be known as a GH liquid, and transparent *glass* a GH solid. They are both transparent to the visible spectrum and also said to be opaque to the infrared. Of course, the reality is – as deduced by this investigation – water and glass are TE and no more special than other matter, even if they are not claimed to be. Thermoelectric glass is the reason Tyndall did not use glass to contain the gases in his experiment; he instead used (presumably non-TE) salt crystals. It is also why IR thermal cameras do not use it.

4.4.3.3 Non-TE Gases, Solids and Liquids

While the atmospheric gases N₂ and O₂, as reasoned in this investigation, are non-TE, so too are Hydrogen (H₂), Helium (He) and possibly Argon, all for the same physical reasons, as we shall come to see. Interestingly, liquid Oxygen is non-TE just as its gaseous form; it will not generate an EMF at any temperature. Non-TE solids include Germanium (Ge), Sodium Chloride (NaCl) – or salt plates (as used in Tyndall’s experiment); Potassium Bromide (KBr); and, to some extent, the plastics.

As a final word for the gases: it is no coincidence these non-TE gases above are known as – in the case of GH theory – ‘the non-GHGs’; and we must remind ourselves they are (wrongly) assumed not to absorb IR heat, when the fact is they are simply non-TE, and have been misinterpreted.

4.4.4 Thermoelectric Interpretation of the Atmosphere

I contest, as stated above in 4.3.7, the assumption that IR spectrometers radiate samples, and claim the spectrographs show the thermoelectric dipole moments or emission spectra of the said (atmospheric) gases, within the EMS. They are the only gases able to be detected by the thermoelectric transducer/sensors. The thermoelectric infrared (TE/IR) spectrograph of the IR atmosphere is shown (below): the only difference from the former interpretation is that the spectrograph is produced by the difference between transduced – measured in thermal EMF voltage – sample (IR radiation) and a reference source’s IR (1500°C) radiation.

Figure 24. Thermo-electromotive Force and the Electromagnetic Spectrum. Thermoelectric vibration modes identified by thermoelectric transducers, currently known as the greenhouse atmosphere. The Raman modes are missing.

The black line in the absorption interpretation is explained by ‘intensity’ or ‘transmittance’ – inferring the samples are radiated; with the thermoelectric interpretation it shows the measured electricity production (EMF) from the heat source – at that particular frequency or wavenumber – and the dips show lower voltage, as the heat radiation from these sample gases measured is at a considerably lower energy (temperature) than the control heat source; i.e. it is cooler.

It should be noted: 'IR spectrometers' need to be purged of the thermoelectric (greenhouse) gases before use; this is to be sure only the heat source is measured and not any other thermoelectric gas.

It should be made clear that the above modes do absorb and emit IR radiation as claimed – this is not contested in this investigation; the point of this paper is to say they are not the only modes to do this. Notwithstanding this, it does not mean the instrument operates as assumed: the samples are not radiated, just as the glass is not radiated in the above hand /glass IR thermometer demonstration. Also, if they did radiate the sample, then, by the law of equipartition, all matter should interact with the (IR) 'light', and all modes – whether TE/IR or TE Raman.

4.4.4.1 Spectroscopy Beer-Lambert Law

Below (Figure 25) is a schematic that shows how spectrometers produce what they display. Again, the samples are not being radiated as such; rather, the detectors measure the difference between the reference radiation and the sample radiation.

Figure 25. UV Spectrometer [43]

Spectrographs are said to be determined in terms of **transmittance** (T) through the sample by the following equation:

$$T = I / I_0$$

Where **I** is said to be the **light intensity** after it passes through the sample, and **I₀** is the **initial light intensity**. Again, this interpretation overlooks the role of thermoelectric transducers and the thermoelectric properties of the substances being measured.

4.4.4.2 Blackbody Measurement

The control tube, or reference cell, of the 'IR' spectrometer, will measure only the electricity produced from – what is termed – a 'black body' heat source, and nothing else, and not the common air in the tube (mainly N₂ and O₂). This is because the 'air' is not thermoelectric.

4.4.5 Analysis of the CO₂ Thermoelectric Emission Absorption Spectra

Below is TE/IR spectrograph for CO₂: it clearly shows CO₂'s absorption bands that are shared electric dipole moments – at **2349cm⁻¹** and **667cm⁻¹**; however, what it does not show, is CO₂'s 3rd symmetric (no electric dipole moment) band at **1388cm⁻¹** – thought there is a small hint of it in the figure at that wavenumber.

Figure 26. CO₂ transmission spectra. [44]

Below is the inverse diagram of the above spectrograph, showing the absorption bands of the molecule. Again, the strength of the greenhouse gas CO₂ is shown. Note the absence of the symmetric vibration modes (B) in the spectrograph and only the presence of asymmetric vibration modes A, C, and D.

Figure 27. CO₂ Thermoelectric IR Spectra. Showing CO₂'s IR active vibrational modes and one non-IR active. [51] 1538 cm⁻¹ is clearly shown to be absent; incorrectly indicated as 'not IR active' when it is more correctly non-thermoelectric due to symmetric stretch.

4.4.5.1 Atmospheric CO₂ TE/IR Spectra

The figure (28) below shows the effect of CO₂ gas when added (in a clockwise direction) into the sample cell of the TE/IR spectrometer: the greater the concentration, the greater the 667 cm⁻¹ band is indicated. The thermoelectric explanation for this is that the CO₂ addition is at a lower temperature than the 1500 °C reference cell and thus generates a lower EMF at this band. The greater the concentration, the greater the offsetting EMF production; however, it is not enough to outproduce the reference heat source.

Figure 28. Thermoelectric Spectra of CO₂ at 667cm⁻¹. Increased CO₂ concentration – from 0 ppm to 1000 ppm – produces thermal EMF revealing CO₂'s 667 TE band.

Note that the CO₂ EMF is not equal to the heat source, just as the candle flame can still be seen in Figure 8c (Stewart demonstration) with a high concentration of CO₂.

4.5 Modern Applications of the 19th Century Thermopile

Today, the thermoelectric thermopile Tyndall and modern instruments use is ubiquitous and can be found in hardware such as the handheld non-contact IR thermometer, early thermal imaging cameras, and early IR spectrometers. These new technologies all have the same problems Tyndall's discovery in that they register or discriminate the same properties of the substances measured.

We shall now look at each of these instruments and identify the same problems.

4.5.1 The Non-Contact IR Thermometer

The regular non-contact IR thermometer (IR thermometer) shares the same core technology, the thermopile, as used to derive the GHGs, and so it offers an easy to use and relatively cheap device (20 U.S dollars, 2018) to learn and understand the special GHGs. The IR thermometer measures IR radiation from 8 to 14 microns on the electromagnetic spectrum (EMS), in what is termed the atmospheric window [27]. They measure the temperature of most substances quite well, but they must be adjusted for the emissivity of the respective substances; for instance, when used to measure the temperature of shiny metals they do not show the real temperature by some 90% revealing a flaw or issue with the thermopile that must be addressed.

4.5.2 The IR thermometer and the Hand-Glass Demonstration

Figure 29 below shows how the IR thermometer discriminates between different substances, in this case, glass and air. The interpretation of what is happening in this demonstration is right at the core of radiation theory: is it the device is detecting IR thermal radiation or is it generating electricity from special substances? Does glass (specially) absorb IR radiation or is it – compared to the ‘air’ – thermoelectric?

Firstly, (frame A of figure 29) the IR thermometer is pointed at my hand: the temperature of my hand – as indicated – is measured at around 32.9 °C; then (frame B) it is pointed at a 3mm thick pane of glass, and the temperature indicated of the glass is around 21.2 °C.

Figure 29. Non-contact thermoelectric thermometer ‘transparent glass demonstration. Frame A, hand temperature measured directly as 32.9°C and the ambient temperature 23.8 (red light indicates wrong emissivity match); frame B, the temperature of glass measured as 21.2° C (green light indicates correct emissivity match); and Frame C, hand temperature through glass measures at 21.2 °C (the temperature of the glass). Notice the temperature of the ‘air’ is not measured with the instrument, but the glass and the hand.

Lastly (in frame C) the gun is pointed at my hand with the glass in between. Before knowing the indicated temperature the question is: will the IR thermometer measure the temperature of my hand – through the glass, or will it measure the temperature of the glass? Most answer, when asked, it is the hand that is measured. This is wrong. When the same visibly transparent glass is placed between my hand and the device, it does not measure my hand’s temperature, but the temperature of the glass; in fact the instrument does not detect my (indicated) 32.9°C hand at all, but shows the same temperature as frame B, 21.2°C. My hand – through the glass – is visible to the eye, but is invisible, or opaque, to the IR thermometer. Right here, there is a divide in interpretation of what’s happening: one by radiation and greenhouse reasoning where the glass is absorbing – as if it is radiated by a beam of IR photons – the IR radiation from my hand; and the other by thermoelectric (TE) reasoning – the glass is thermoelectric and is generating a current proportional to the radiant temperature (or energy).

The fact is the glass is TE as explained in the section above: glass is a thermoelectric substance.

There is another question that can be posited from this demonstration – which will help to understand the derivation of greenhouse and current radiation theory – and that is:

what is not being measured? Or, what is not mentioned, in frame A other than my hand and the detector? It is the ambient air* (temperature) between my hand and the detector. (* assumes= 100% N₂ and O₂ mix)

While being visibly transparent, air*; (as claimed in this paper) is non-TE – unlike the (similarly) visibly transparent glass in frame B and the of the said GHGs. There is a paradox here and it is the air* in this demonstration (and universally) does – of course – have an ‘ambient’ temperature; however, an IR thermoelectric thermometer cannot, and will not, measure the air* temperature – whether at ambient room temperature (if the room temperature were measured by a regular thermometer), or whether outside – in extreme sub 0°C, or conversely, high temperatures.

Returning to frame A (figure 4): what if the same demonstration was undertaken in a bath of GH (or TE) gas – say CO₂? What would the detector measure then? Of course, it will measure the temperature of the CO₂, and not my hand – just in the same way it measured the glass in frame C. If we can describe and understand CO₂ to be TE we should equally be able to describe and understand glass to be ‘a GH solid’.

The outstanding question from this demonstration – that is addressed directly in this paper – is whether or not the air* absorbs and emits IR photons: the Raman Exhaust Report shows it does.

4.5.3 CO₂ Sensors

Regular CO₂ concentration sensors use a thermopile transducer – exploiting the Seebeck effect (though this is not how they are explained in most references [46],[47], [48], [49]). In general, the operation is similar to the IR thermometer and the hand-glass demonstration above in figure 3, and demonstrations in figures 5 and 6. Instead of measuring the temperature of my hand through the glass, the CO₂ sensor is more controlled. To measure the concentration of a sample, the sample is let in between a constant reference heat source, and the thermopile detector. Then a ratio calculation of the difference in signal between a sample and a reference heat source is computed. In principle, a 100% sample of CO₂ will transduce more than the heat source and in effect block out the heat source by 100%.

4.5.4 ‘IR’ Thermal Imaging Cameras

Using the same principle as the ‘spot measuring’ IR thermometer, the IR thermal imaging camera measures an array of thermoelectric ‘spots’, able to be viewed – with modern screen technology. ‘IR’ cameras originality used a thermopile thermoelectric detectors [50][51]; modern array detectors are more sophisticated, but all are based on either voltage, resistance or current, ‘production’ when heated by IR radiation. The principle is the same, and the proof of this is all detectors measure the same substances – as Tyndall – in the same way; they equally cannot measure the likes of N₂ and O₂. It is, for this reason, I will term them as thermoelectric IR cameras or TE/IR cameras. Maybe someday they will be correctly named thermoelectric imagery.

Unlike traditional light sensing cameras, the TE/IR camera – as with the ‘IR thermometer’ cannot use glass for its lenses – as glass is TE, or as it is said to be, opaque to IR radiation. Instead, the lenses (figure 30 below) are made of one of the few non-TE substances that is solid, Germanium (Ge). Germanium is said to be – just as with N₂ and O₂ and air’ – ‘transparent’ to IR radiation, Pg. 5 [52] and [53],[54]: a thermoelectric interpretation may say it is simply non-, or at least less, thermoelectric. In frame A the presenter holds a piece of glass between the camera and a heat source, revealing the ‘opaque’ property of glass in

the camera image; in frame B he holds a germanium camera lenses, and in frame C, places a lenses between the camera and the heat source revealing the transparent property of Germanium to the camera.

Figure 30. Demonstrating with the thermal imaging camera: (A) ‘opaque’ thermoelectric glass in front of the heat source; (B) visibly opaque germanium in hand; (C) ‘transparent’ non-thermoelectric germanium placed in front of heat source [55].

Germanium presents the same paradox of TE detectors to the air: they do not measure temperature. But what if the germanium was hot? I could heat up a lump of germanium to a dangerous temperature, but unlike a regular thermometer, TE/IR thermometers, or TE/IR cameras, would not register its temperature – and its danger; just as it does not register the temperature of the (hot) ‘air’.

4.5.4.1 The Germanium Sauna

As a thought experiment: imagine a ‘hot’ sauna made entirely made of germanium: what temperature would an IR thermometer or camera measure if measured within the sauna? It would indicate – unlike the traditional thermometer – the temperature outside the sauna: it would ‘see’ right through the walls (apart, of course, for the water vapour and other trace gases, and the people inside). As a thermometer, it would be useless. As silly as this may sound, this scenario – which could be created, though it would be expensive – is exactly what a TE/IR camera does in the free $\pm 300\text{K}^{\circ}$ atmosphere; it only detects the objects that are thermoelectric.

4.5.4.2 Greenhouse Gases and Thermography

To Show the effects different gases have on thermoelectric transducers; in another (Youtube clip, figure 31 below) demonstration using the thermal imaging camera – ‘thermoelectric’ camera – Infrared absorption of a greenhouse gas: two concealed glass cylinders are shown (frame A): the cylinder on the in the left is filled with ‘air’, and on the right the cylinder is filled with “a greenhouse gas” – presumably CO₂. Frame B shows the left-hand glass full of air to be “transparent to IR radiation”, and in Frame C, the GHG is shown to be opaque. Again, with knowledge of thermoelectrics this conclusion is an illusion, and wrong – the air is not thermoelectric.

Figure 31. Thermal imaging camera Greenhouse gas demonstration. (A), two glasses, one fill with air (mostly N₂ and O₂) and the other with a GHG, presumably CO₂; (B), the first glass is non-thermoelectric, wrongly said to be ‘transparent to IR’; and C, the GHG is thermoelectric, wrongly said to be opaque to IR. [56]

To defend this claim; firstly, notice the glass cylinders of ‘air’ and GHG are contained using a thin plastic ‘kitchen’ wrap: this is not for convenience, thin plastic is known to be “transparent to IR radiation” or, in keeping thermoelectrics, is more correctly interpreted as being non-thermoelectric. This containment problem has significant to the Tyndall experiment (above) as he had too had the same problem containing the gases in his mid 19th Century experiment, and used rock salt crystal (which is still used in laboratories today). The point being he did not use glass. Secondly, the appears not to have a temperature; but the ‘air’ does have (must have) a temperature – else it is contravening thermodynamics and quantum mechanics as it is matter and so must be radiating. By thermoelectrics, the thermopile is generating electricity off the radiation of the TE gas, and as the TE gas in the line of sight of the camera detector, it is the incident TE gas, and not the background hand of the demonstrator, that is measured.

So far I am only using end-use instruments; later I will get into the physics and chemistry behind these instruments: what we will see is this is only half the story.

4.5.4.3 Non-Thermoelectric Liquid Oxygen

In another simple and normally trivial video demonstration on thermography (figure 32), liquid oxygen – at a temperature of less than 90K – is interpreted to be transparent to infrared (below); however, with the knowledge of thermoelectrics what has been demonstrated is liquid oxygen (also – like the oxygen gas) is not thermoelectric, and the magnet in the Dura cup is.

Figure 32 Thermal imaging camera liquid oxygen demonstration. Frame A shows a visible image, showing a magnet in a cup of (90K) liquid oxygen; and in frame B, a thermoelectric infrared image, again showing the magnet, and importantly, not showing the liquid oxygen. [57]

If it were any other liquid, except liquid nitrogen, the image of the magnet would not be shown in the FLIR image. The conclusion of these demonstrations is that oxygen does not show with thermoelectric transducers.

4.5.4.4 The BBC Dr. Stewart GHG Demonstration

In BBC's documentary: 'The Climate Wars'[58] Dr Stewart demonstrates the greenhouse effect using a thermal imaging camera; unbeknownst to Dr Stewart, it appears, is that he is reconstructing the original 1859 Tyndall experiment, only with modern materials and technology (as shown in Figure 33 below). The thermal imaging camera (frame B) serves as a substitute for the single thermopile, and thin plastic (frame A) at either end of the 'glass' tubes contains the gases.

Figure 33. Dr Stewart YouTube clip [58], [59]. Demonstrating the greenhouse effect. Frame A shows the gas contained behind thin plastic, B. thermal image of a flame through 'air'; and C. CO₂ blocking the flame out.

An image of the candle is seen on a screen via the TE/IR camera link (frame A), and as the heavier than air CO₂ is released into the sealed cylinder, the bright candle image from the camera disappears, from the bottom up, and is replaced by the blue colour screen (frame C). Dr Stewart concludes – just as John Tyndall did: *“The CO₂ absorbs the infrared or is essentially trapping the heat from the candle.”*

If this claim is valid, the claim must be said and understood in full knowledge of (the above) thermoelectric theory and practical application of infrared instruments, including thermal imaging cameras and thermopiles. If in the experiment the electricity generating ability of the said (and inferred) gases and solids – via the Seebeck Effect – were disclosed and understood – i.e. an understanding of how the thermal imaging camera discriminates between IR active and IR inactive substances at the particular spectrum range observed – a different conclusion would be drawn, and Dr Stewart’s conclusion wrong.

With this being said, the alternative interpretation and conclusion of both the Tyndall experiment and the modern laboratory ‘Stewart’ experiment (above) may read as follows. The first thermal image (frame B) shows the bright flickering candle. This is due to the ‘air’ (close to 100% N₂ and O₂) within the tube, the thin plastic sheet at either end of the tube, the air between the camera and the tube, and finally the lenses of the camera (most probably made of Germanium), all being non-thermoelectric/non-TE. Only the incident flame is thermoelectric, and hence – given the camera display is calibrated for the hot flame and not its background radiation – the flame’s image is displayed. The next scene (frame C) shows the flame image slowly changing to a blue colour as the CO₂ gas is released into the tube: it is the incident CO₂ that now generates electricity proportional to the temperature.

4.5.5 The Hairdryer Paradox Explained

With a first-principles knowledge of thermoelectrics, an explanation can be found for this discrepancy, which will lead us to a hypothesis. The thermal ‘outlet blast’ image blown onto a surface implies this surface is thermoelectric, and the air is not. If there were no surface there at all, or if the surface were of solid–not–thermoelectric Germanium, maybe salt crystal (more on this later), no heat by the thermoelectric detector would be detected. As a matter of interest, one may ask: how would the thermogram appear if the hairdryer were: (1) fed only with CO₂; and (2) if the dryer were submerged in a ‘bath’ of only CO₂? Reasoning by thermoelectrics, for the former (1), it would show a plume of ‘bright-hot’ outflow. For the later (2), no discernable image would be observed as it will be the incident temperature CO₂ measured by the thermoelectric detector.

4.5.5.1 White Body Cavity /Air Experiment

To further emphasise this flaw with thermoelectric detectors, as the hair dryer paradox attempts, suppose the following experiment. In the tradition of ‘blackbody radiation’, fill a cavity made of shiny gold (an assumed perfect white body IR ‘reflector’), with N₂ and O₂ (‘air’), and radiate IR photons (heat) from a centrally positioned electric element. This poses a paradox, as none of these ingredients absorb IR, leaving us with the question: what would happen to the temperature of the gases and the gold? As shiny gold has one to the lowest emissivities possible (of 0.025), and ‘air’ (as it is assumed) does not absorb, current assumptions would suggest no heating of the gases and the gold. A pragmatic, common sense view would suggest the converse – the gases and gold would heat somewhat proportional to the energy radiated.

4.5.6 Paradoxes Associated with Emissivity

Emissivity is not without contradiction, for instance it assumes shiny metals hardly radiate; and snow and ice are near-perfect black bodies. Emissivity is a definitive measure of radiation of matter and has a value ranging from the value of 0 to 1: but seen here, it too presents deep paradoxes. The following is outside the scope of the study, but requires a mention as it was found while researching this paper emissivity is not the only used in direct association with thermoelectric detectors, but it is itself determined by thermoelectric thermopile detectors. If there is a mistake made in radiation physics by using thermoelectrics in isolation, this is only compounded by using thermoelectrics to define the problem with thermoelectrics.

As strange as this may sound, it is all-true; and further reconciling this problem will be the topic of another study. Notwithstanding this, this study has led the author to conclude emissivity is no more than a correction factor between the real temperature of an object and the thermoelectric indicated temperature (itself determined by the Seebeck effect and not accurate).

4.6 Other Applications of Raman Spectroscopy: Revealing IR Radiating N₂ and O₂ (and CO₂'s Raman 1338 cm⁻¹)

The following are some of the few applications of Raman monitoring.

More examples are listed in Appendix 8.1.

4.6.1 Measuring Atmospheric Gas Concentrations (Keeling Curve) with Raman

The fact that Raman devices can measure gas concentrations – as demonstrated in the RER – has implications on the measurement of GH gas concentrations. Indeed it has been found and suggested even the Keeling curve of GH gases – namely CO₂ – need not be measured by TE/IR thermoelectrics alone, which they are today. The GH gases can be measured by Raman Lasers, just as they are on Solar system space probes; this is demonstrated in the following paper:

A Raman scattering method for precise measurement of atmospheric oxygen balance

Abstract

*Quantitative measurements of Raman scattering intensities from N₂, O₂, and CO₂ under ambient atmospheric conditions are given. The atmosphere was illuminated with 20,489 cm⁻¹ Ar⁺ laser radiation. These scattering intensities are sufficiently strong to **allow measurement of O₂/N₂ and CO₂/N₂ concentration ratios in the atmosphere to a precision of 0.3 and 0.006 ppm total atmosphere, respectively, by means of scattered photon counting over a 174-hour integration period. The Raman technique represents an improvement in precision over existing techniques by almost two orders of magnitude, and a substantial but less easily determined improvement in accuracy by using the transition probabilities of a monomolecular reference gas as a standard, rather than the properties of a mixed gas standard as is done in current measurements. [60]***

Analysis of influence of atmosphere extinction to Raman Lidar monitoring CO₂ concentration profile*

"Lidar (Light detection and ranging) system monitoring of the atmosphere is a novel and powerful technique tool. The Raman lidar is well established today as a leading research tool in the study of numerous important areas in the atmospheric sciences. In this paper, the

principle of Raman lidar technique measurement CO₂ concentration profile is presented... [61]

NDACC are using Raman Lidar to measure H₂O, with N₂ as “a reference molecule having a well-known mixing ratio throughout the altitude range considered” [62]

This process is also discussed by the IEEE under: LIDAR FOR ATMOSPHERIC TRACE GAS DETECTION [63], and in a paper “Relative Raman Cross Section for N₂, O₂, CO, CO₂, SO₂, and H₂S”[64]: where an (inferred) argon ion laser (5145Å) is used to identify the gases.

Also see appendix 7.8 for more on atmospheric Raman Lidar.

4.6.2 Raman Solar System Probe Applications

On modern-day solar system space probes Raman detectors are becoming the detector of choice: it makes sense, the detect oxygen and CH₄ – accentual part indicators of the existence of life – and CO₂, and N₂. In the review ‘**Remote Raman Spectroscopy of Minerals at Elevated Temperature 2012**’ [65]

Raman was extensively evaluated for its obvious complementary merits.

*“..thus, using strictly visible light sources and receivers Raman spectroscopy **can yield complementary information** about the vibrational transitions observed in infrared emission or reflection spectra.”*

This statement was followed by a standard misunderstanding (as interpreted for this research) between Raman and TE/IR: the following is not consistent with the findings of this paper.

“ Raman spectroscopy is not directly equivalent to infrared (IR) spectroscopy, as the strengths of individual features can be quite different between IR and Raman spectroscopy due to different selection rules. The activity of Raman vibrational modes is a function of the change in polarizability during the vibrational mode, whereas the activity of infrared modes is associated with the change in permanent dipole moment during a normal mode of molecular vibration. Raman spectra of samples contain a wealth of information that can be used to identify minerals and chemical compounds based on the vibrational frequencies, relative intensities, and number of bands in the spectra.”

4.6.2.1 Venus

Below (figure 34) is a Raman spectra of Venus’s atmosphere. Notice CO₂ is measured (at its 1338 cm⁻¹ mode. If this mode is good enough for Venus, why not Planet Earth? If TE/IR were used on Venus, no N₂ or O₂ would be measured – at any temperature.

Gas phase (Raman lines)

Gaseous components in Venus atmosphere

Possible compounds in Venus atmospheric aerosol

Alian Wang, WSU

Figure 34. Venus Atmosphere ‘Raman Lines’ Showing molecules with their respective modes in Venus’s atmosphere. [66]

4.6.3 Other Uses for Raman Spectroscopy

See Appendix 7.1 of other uses for Raman, including: measuring automobile emissions; Raman SCattering AnaLyzers (RASCAL), Geology CO₂ 1388 cm⁻¹ ; CO₂’s 1388cm⁻¹ Excitation, and the ‘Dicke effect’ (see appendix).

4.7 Evidence of Raman and TE-IR Modes (N₂’s 2338 cm⁻¹) Radiating IR

For the Raman theory – of a radiating ‘non-GHG’ atmosphere – to have any validity, there should be instances that show coherence with the theory. The following are instances where the non-GHG modes are radiated, and in total compliance with quantum mechanics offer such examples: the CO₂ laser and absorbing thermosphere N₂ molecules – where there is only radiation as a transfer of heat-energy.

4.7.1 CO₂ Laser: A Practical Application of ‘Radiated N₂ at 2338 cm⁻¹’

The CO₂ Laser offers a pragmatic real-life application – or kind of experiment – invoking and testing both of the key atmospheric gases in question, N₂ and CO₂, revealing their real relationship between them when they are radiated – though it is not currently interpreted as so. After an understanding of the CO₂ Laser process it could be assumed – contrary to standard belief – N₂ in the atmosphere is the gas that affects – and actually forces – the CO₂.

All theory surrounding the CO₂ Laser points to the role of N₂ has in ‘pumping’ the CO₂ as an essential part of the process; so much so – it is explained in all textbooks – the laser will not operate without this ‘absorbing/emitting’ property of N₂ when radiated. The relationship is so close that these lasers are technically termed **N₂-CO₂ Lasers**. A closer look at the physics behind the laser reveals N₂’s true nature, and its absorption property at its **2338cm⁻¹** mode; a property ignored in atmospheric ‘GH’ theory. It is as if the scientist

describing the CO₂ laser is oblivious to the ramifications this knowledge would have for GH theory; that they are using the very same mechanics – both physics and chemistry – that the Raman measurements point to in the atmosphere; only here, the gas is excited at the said modes.

4.7.1.1 The CO₂-N₂ Laser

Lasers all have the following key components:

1. An active medium – for the CO₂-N₂ laser it is the CO₂ and N₂ that are of interest;
2. Energy input/ pumping source/ high voltage discharge
3. Optical Feedback, this is not of interest in the investigation
4. Population inversion, this is essential – more electrons must be in an excited state than the lower state; this is very important.

Fig. 1.1. System developed by Patel (1964b) demonstrating laser emission due to transfer of vibrational energy from N₂ to CO₂.

Figure 35. [67]

"Infrared laser emission from CO₂ was first reported by Patel (1964) and others in pulsed discharges through pure CO₂. In this system, N₂ is excited in an electric discharge to form vibrationally excited N₂ molecules, which stream into an interaction region to mix with unexcited CO₂. The CO₂ is vibrationally excited through the reaction, which occurs efficiently. Pg. 1 [67]

The following is an excerpt from a paper on how a CO₂ laser operates from the book LASER PHYSICS by PETER W. MILONNI JOSEPH H. EBERLY, page 51 [68]. It is a typical description of how the CO₂ laser directly implicates N₂'s 2338 cm⁻¹ mode. I have posted the direct text to show this is standard knowledge. It is essential to look out for the Wavenumbers of the gases, particularly N₂'s 2330 cm⁻¹ and CO₂'s 1388 cm⁻¹, and their role in the laser process.

"The electric-discharge carbon dioxide laser has a population inversion mechanism similar in some respects to the He-Ne laser: the upper CO₂ laser level is pumped by excitation transfer from the nitrogen molecule, with N₂ itself excited by electron impact. The relevant energy levels of the CO₂ and N₂ molecules are vibrational-rotational levels of their electronic ground states. We discussed the vibrational-rotational characteristics of the CO₂ molecule in Section 2.5. We indicated in Fig. 2.10 the relative energy scales of the three normal modes of

vibration, the so-called symmetric stretch, bending, and asymmetric stretch modes (Fig. 2.9). Like all diatomic molecules, N_2 has a single “ladder” of vibrational levels corresponding to a single mode of vibration (Fig. 2.7) (2338cm^{-1}). In Fig. 11.9, we show the CO_2 and N_2 vibrational energy level diagrams side by side. Figure 11.9 shows that the first excited vibrational level ($v = 1$) of the N_2 molecule lies close to the level (001) of CO_2 . Due to this near resonance, rapid excitation transfer occurs between N_2 ($v = 1$) and $CO_2(001)$, the upper laser level. N_2 ($v = 1$) is itself a long-lived (metastable) level, so it effectively stores energy for eventual transfer to

Figure 11.9 Vibrational energy levels of CO_2 and N_2 . The energies are given in cm^{-1} , a unit corresponding to a frequency $(\nu)(1\text{ cm}^{-1}) \approx 3.0 \times 10^{10}\text{ Hz}$, or an energy $h\nu \approx 1.2 \times 10^{-4}\text{ eV}$.

Figure 36.

$CO_2(001)$; it is also efficiently pumped by electron-impact excitation. As in the case of the He-Ne laser, therefore, advantage is taken of a fortuitous near resonance between an excited state of the lasing species and an excited, long-lived collision partner. Laser action in CO_2 lasers occurs on the vibrational transition $(001) \rightarrow (100)$ of CO_2 . This transition has a wave number around $(2349-1388)\text{ cm}^{-1} \approx 961\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 11.9), or a wavelength around $(961\text{ cm}^{-1})^{-1} \approx 10.4\text{ mm}$ in the infrared. The laser wavelength also depends on the rotational quantum numbers of the upper and lower laser levels. For the case in which the upper and lower levels are characterized by $J = 19$ and 20 , respectively, the wavelength is about 10.6 mm , the most common CO_2 laser wavelength. The (100) and (020) vibrational levels of CO_2 are essentially resonant. This “accidental degeneracy” results in a strong quantum mechanical coupling in which states in effect lose their separate identities.

Furthermore the (010) and (020) levels undergo a very rapid vibration-to-vibration (VV) energy transfer:

For practical purposes, then, the stimulated emission on the $(001) \rightarrow (100)$ vibrational band takes CO_2 molecules from (001) to (010) . The (010) level thus acts in effect like a lower laser level that must be rapidly “knocked out” in order to avoid a bottleneck in the population inversion.

Fortunately, it is relatively easy to de-excite the (010) level by vibration-to-translation (VT) processes:

where *A* represents some collision partner. The VT de-excitation of (010) effectively depopulates the lower laser level and also puts CO₂ molecules in the ground level, where they can be pumped to the upper laser level by the VV excitation transfer

In high-power CO₂ lasers the lifetime of the CO₂(010) level may be on the order of 1 ms due to collisions of CO₂ with He, N₂, and CO₂ itself. Of course, the VT process (11.7.2) is exothermic and results in a heating of the laser medium; some of the other VT and VV processes in the CO₂ laser have the same effect. This heating of the laser medium is a very serious problem in high-power lasers. In the next section we will see how it may be overcome. Electron impacts excite CO₂ as well as N₂ vibrations. “

4.7.1.2 Stimulated and Spontaneous Emission

‘Stimulated’ and ‘Spontaneous’ Emission are quantum mechanical features, and together point to the absorption and emission of photons of light. In the case of the CO₂ laser, it is the ‘stimulated’ and ‘spontaneous’ emission and absorption of IR photons between N₂ and CO₂ molecules. It, on its own, stands as a proof of emission and absorption of N₂ of light photons.

4.7.1.3 Radiating N₂: CO₂ LASER – Discussions

Here, with the CO₂ laser it is shown N₂ – a non-GHG that should not be able to absorb any (IR) radiation from any ‘particle’ whether photon or electron – is first excited or energised (heated up) at its **2338** cm⁻¹ mode so as to further excite (heat up) the CO₂ molecules **2349** cm⁻¹ mode. This is in total contradiction to GH theory where N₂ is assumed not to absorb any radiation. This application shows it is N₂ that directly affects, and excites the CO₂ molecule – though they do claim it is by collision and not radiation.

4.7.1.4 The CO₂ Laser, and the Question of Radiation?

The Laser demonstrates how different substances are excited when ‘fired upon’ by electrons through an electrical discharge in a cathode ray tube. The important question for this investigation is: does this ‘firing upon’ constitute as radiation – as a transfer of energy? This is important because N₂ is assumed not to absorb radiation.

4.7.1.5 Is Discharge of Electrons Radiation?

The following are quotes from the first lines of Wikipedia:

“Thermal radiation is electromagnetic radiation generated by the thermal motion of charged particles in matter.” [69]

Do the ‘discharged electrons’ used to excite the N₂ at its **2338** cm⁻¹ constitute ‘charged particles’ (from the above definition)?

“In physics, a charged particle is a particle with an electric charge. It may be an ion, such as a molecule or atom with a surplus or deficit of electrons relative to protons. It can be the electrons and protons themselves, as well as other elementary particles, like positrons.” [70]

It can be deduced cathode rays are a form of radiation. From this, the fired electrons are charged particles, and they radiate thermal (IR) energy – the N₂ at its **2338** cm⁻¹ mode absorbs this energy.

4.7.1.6 Frank-Hertz Experiment

To support this claim, non-TE-IR modes radiate, the Frank-Hertz experiment shows that electrons, from a variable electrical discharge, affect a gas molecule to reveal its emission spectrum mode – the spectrum predicted by the quantum mechanical Schrödinger equation. It can be shown to work for all gases. Even without radiation – it is assumed to be by ‘collision’ – the Frank-Hertz experiment shows N₂ absorbs, and thus emits. From this, it is plausible that energy is transferred from its excited 2338 cm⁻¹ to CO₂'s 2349 cm⁻¹ from emission of its mode.

4.7.1.7 Collisions Implausible: Convection Paradox

If excitation were solely due to collisions, it would imply conduction as a means of energy transfer. However, it can be shown that this is unlikely, as N₂ has a very low conduction coefficient of 0.024 k. Therefore, this form of transfer is doubtful.

4.7.1.8 Implications for IR Spectroscopy

To conclude from the CO₂ Laser and show the implications of it on IR spectroscopy, the symmetric vibrational modes of N₂ and O₂, and CO₂'s 1388 cm⁻¹ – assumed ‘non-IR active’ as they do not emit or absorb IR radiation due to their lack of a dipole – has been refuted. The ‘symmetric stretch’ N₂ mode excites the CO₂, having been radiated. Not only does the N₂'s symmetric mode vibrate from radiant excitation, heating, and so forcing the CO₂ up an energy level, but CO₂'s symmetric vibration (at **1388** cm⁻¹) is affected – or necessarily implicated in the process by the equipartition principle in what can arguably only be by radiation (by photon collision). Atmospheric CO₂ exhibits the same 1388 cm⁻¹ symmetric mode, but there is no mention of this in atmospheric spectra or its effect on climate forcing; it is assumed not to be part of the standard model, and this assumption will need to be revisited.

4.7.1.9 N₂ and Kirchhoff's Law

Kirchhoff's Law states, ‘Good absorber, good emitter.’ As it can be shown, N₂ is absorbing charged electron particles from the electron discharge as if from radiation, in compliance with quantum mechanics: by Kirchhoff's Law, it is equally, by definition, said to be a ‘good emitter’.

4.7.1.10 Metastable N₂ and the Greenhouse Atmosphere

I shall first define metastable and then discuss it in terms of N₂ and CO₂.

*“Metastable state, in physics and chemistry, particular excited state of an atom, nucleus, or other system that **has a longer lifetime than the ordinary excited states** and that generally has a shorter lifetime than the lowest, often stable, energy state, called the ground state. A metastable state may thus be considered a kind of temporary energy trap or a somewhat stable intermediate stage of a system the energy of which may be lost in discrete amounts. In quantum mechanical terms, transitions from metastable states are “forbidden” and are much less probable than the “allowed” transitions from other excited states.” [71]*

N₂ is said to be **Metastable** – long-lasting (absorption) – and this property is central to the CO₂ laser; the (greenhouse) gas CO₂ is not said to be metastable.

This metastable N₂ has ramifications for greenhouse theory, as N₂ is the Earth's atmosphere's major constituent gas. This is not to say the atmosphere is a laser (though experts for other planets discuss this); it is only to say N₂ has this property when excited, and this is supported by experiment. [72],[73] And may be assumed to be a property of the troposphere atmosphere as well. Meschad – on the topic of planetary lasers and metastable N₂ – says:

“The occupation of the upper laser level is possible directly, but is much more favourable with the addition of nitrogen. Metastable N₂ levels not only can discharge but also can transfer the energy to the CO₂ molecules very profitably as well.” (Pg. 274 [74])

4.7.1.11 Metastable N₂ from ‘Collisions’ and not Radiation

All explanations of metastable N₂ in the context of the CO₂ laser do not point to radiation, but rather support the non-radiating N₂ hypothesis, where it is all explained by collisions.

“ Electron collisions excite date nitrogen molecules to their vibrational level. Once in this level, the nitrogen molecules are metastable, they cannot really lose energy radiatively and can only return to the ground state as a result of collisions. Because nitrogen is a homo nuclear diatomic molecule, it vibrates and has no dipole moment; a dipole moment is needed for spontaneous emission to occur. The population of N₂ molecules builds up and these molecules transport fare their excitation to CO₂ molecules, thereby populating the upper CO₂ laser level.” (P.220)[75]

Here again we have a problem, a paradox: does ‘collision’, by electrons or photons, at this level, constitute radiation? I say it does, but if it does, this is a striking and damning revelation, totally contradicting GH theory. Equally, if it doesn't, it stands as a contradiction to quantum mechanics, where all matter is said to radiate, including accelerated electrons.

The reason given for this metastable N₂ assumption is that it does not emit photons when excited; however, I believe this needs to be reviewed, as it is, on its own, a repeat of the mistakes made in GH theory, where diatomics (N₂ and O₂) are assumed not to radiate. I believe, based on the discoveries from this investigation, it is a ‘throwback’ to a lone reliance on ‘IR’ – thermo-electric – radiation theory that is the problem. N₂ can be shown (as it has been attempted in this paper) to emit IR photons. If it is that N₂ emits and absorbs radiation, the assumption that N₂ is metastable because it does not emit suggests that radiation theory is incomplete.

4.7.1.12 Natural CO₂ Lasers

NASA and others have discovered natural lasers on the likes of Mars and Venus [76] and below [77] It is demonstrated how they, in a similar way to the laboratory ones, operate. Again, this repeats the role that radiation has on atmospheric gases.

“000 to 101 followed by a resonant collisional energy transfer of a V3 quantum to another CO₂ molecule (2349cm⁻¹), which is similar to the laboratory CO₂ laser (Fig 8.6).”

Fig. 8.6 Molecular physics of a natural CO₂ laser. Radiative and collisional processes affecting the pumping of this laser in the mesospheres of Mars and Venus are identified.

Figure 37.

4.7.2 'Blackbody CO₂ Laser' Showing N₂ Heated by Sunlight

It is challenging to directly show N₂ is directly radiated by the sun's energy, absorbing IR photons; however, the following experiment shows indirect confirmation of the hypothesis: N₂ is 'heated' (and heats) - i.e. absorbs (and emits) - by sunlight.

The extract below is taken directly from the 'NASA Technical Paper': A Blackbody-Pumped CO₂-N₂ Transfer Laser, by Young and Higdon. [78].

"One laser concept that may achieve such efficiencies is the blackbody-pumped CO₂ transfer laser. Such a system is called a fluid-mixing or transfer gas-dynamic laser and is shown in conceptual form in figure 1.

Figure 1. A conceptual design of a space-based blackbody N₂-CO₂ transfer laser.

Figure 38. Demonstrating N₂ Excitation from the Sun.

*In this system, a black body cavity is heated by collected sunlight ('solar power') to a temperature of approximately 2000 K. **Nitrogen gas passing through the cavity is heated to the same temperature as the black body.** The vibrationally excited N₂ then passes through a nozzle into a low-pressure laser cavity. Here, CO₂ and He are mixed with the vibrationally excited N₂. A coincidence between N₂ (v=1) (**2338 cm⁻¹**) and the 001 asymmetric longitudinal mode (**2349 cm⁻¹**) of CO₂ allows rapid transfer of the N₂ (v = 1) vibrational energy into the CO₂ 001 upper laser level. Lasing commences between the 001 and the 100 levels at 10.6 microns. "*

4.7.2.1 Experimental Setup

"Standard purity N₂ flowed through a quartz tube within an electrically heated cavity, which in the present experiment simulates a solar-heated blackbody cavity. The oven temperature and pressure were monitored. The gas velocity was slow enough (226 cm/sec) to allow the N₂ temperature to come into equilibrium with the oven temperature... CO₂ and He were then mixed with the vibrationally excited N₂ to cause a transfer of energy from the N₂ (v= 1) to the CO₂ upper laser level. "

4.7.2.2 Absorbing N₂: A New Law of Physics?

The experiment shows – consistent with quantum mechanics theory – that electron excitation is equivalent to solar photon excitation (as discussed throughout this paper).

As a consequence, concentrated light photons heat the N₂ by the same physics as the CO₂ Laser; only there is no electrical discharge. Again, this process is not allowed in the current

GH theory. Moreover, the experiment demonstrates that CO₂ is 'pumped' or stimulated by N₂ in this process; this behaviour constitutes a law of physics.

4.7.3 N₂ Absorbing in the 'Hot' Thermosphere and the Aurora

N₂ and O₂ are excited by charged particles in the thermosphere and temperatures for these molecules reach up to 2000°C; it is **Raman** devices that are used to measure this temperature, in the lower thermosphere [79]. This provides additional evidence that N₂ and O₂ are directly affected by IR photon radiation: if they absorb, they also emit. It can also be demonstrated that charged particles heat the N₂ atmosphere during an aurora, providing further evidence of absorption.

4.7.4 IR Absorption and Thunder Creation: Lightning Heating the Air

From lightning radiation, the air is heated to 5 to 7 times the temperature of the sun. This radiation is consistent with N₂ absorption of IR photons and may stand as a 'natural' demonstration or experiment of the hypothesised.

4.7.5 IR Absorption and the Incandescent Light Bulb

While looking for supporting evidence of IR absorbing N₂ and O₂ and noticing the hot air is moving around the outside of the bulb when on. I wondered, what if the bulb were filled with air or N₂? What would result: a pressure increase? It turns out bulbs are filled with gas, mostly Argon (Ar) and a small percentage N₂[80]. Neither of these gases is IR (thermoelectric), and they are said to warm inside the bulb by conduction. However, given the pressure inside the bulb is 70% of an atmosphere (to deal with the pressure problem) and Ar and N₂ are both very poor thermal conductors (argon even less than N₂ at 0.016 W/m K [4], it is plausible that the gases heat primarily, if not entirely, by radiation, as I have claimed.

4.7.5.1 Non-TE/IR Non-Raman Argon

In this discussion of IR-absorbing gases, argon presents itself as an odd one out. It is neither a GHG (it is not thermoelectric) nor a Raman-active gas. This is attributed to its vibrational behaviour as an isolated atom. However, Ar has a specific heat capacity of 0.520 (kJ/kg K), compared to air, which is 1.01, and does (albeit at a low rate) conduct heat. The dismissal of its radiating IR may be due to the said detectors being unable to detect its behaviour, just as thermoelectric-IR cannot detect Raman modes. Again, if it does not radiate IR, this is in contradiction to quantum physics.

4.8 Heat Capacity-Radiation Paradox

The discrepancy between the GHGs and the non-GHGs presents another paradox associated with IR radiation theory, which is related to the gases' respective specific heat capacities. All the atmospheric gases have specific heat capacities (Table 3, column 2), indicating that one type of heat transfer directly affects them. The paradox lies in the assumed non-absorption of IR heat energy by radiation from the non-GHGs, which, like all other gases, are very poor conductors of heat (column 3). This leaves only convection, but this is improbable due to the former being poor or exempt (addressed below in 4.8.5). The question is: how can these gases have specific heat capacities if they cannot transfer heat energy, without radiation or conduction, as known and assumed? The only way to reconcile this paradox is to assume that radiation absorption, as demonstrated in this investigation, does occur for the non-GHGs, and presumably at their respective Raman modes.

Table 3. Comparing Gas Specific Heat Capacity with Thermal Conductivity and Radiation Properties. Source: 'engineeringtoolbox.com.

Atmospheric Gas	Specific Heat Capacity - C_p - kJ/(kgK)	Thermal Conductivity - k - w/(mK)	Assumed to Absorb IR Radiation? Yes/No
Ar	0.520	0.016	No
N ₂	1.04	0.024	No
O ₂	0.919	0.024	No
CO ₂	0.844	0.0146	Yes
CH ₄	2.22	0.003	Yes
He	5.19	0.142	No
Air	1.01	0.0262	Only the GHGs

4.8.1 Standard (bottle) Greenhouse Experiments, and SHC Measurement

One of the most popular demonstrations of greenhouse gases is the 'greenhouse bottle experiment'[81] When CO₂ in one bottle and air in another are radiated by thermal radiation and temperature over time, the CO₂ bottle temperature rises the highest, as shown below. However, with knowledge of specific heat theory and the specific heat capacities of the respective gases – not withstanding the difference between constant volume (as assumed in the demonstrations) and constant pressure; I claim is this not an experiment demonstrating the specific heat capacity of air and CO₂, where CO₂ has a low heat capacity relative to air – as described in the following subsection.

Figure 39. Greenhouse Gas Bottle Demonstration [82]. Bottles with CO₂ and air are radiated and temperature measured – CO₂ in blue. Is this not an experiment to measure the heat capacities of the respective gases?

Below (figure 40) is an image taken from a specific heat capacity demonstration; if two more boxes were added showing the effect of air (C_p 1.01) and CO_2 (0.8), it would be understandable the CO_2 would have a higher temperature, concurring with GH demonstrations.

Figure 40. Specific Heat Capacity. The lower the heat capacity, the higher the temperature from single heat source.

4.8.2 Real Measurement of Gas Heat Capacity: Equivalent to GH Demonstrations

In the standard experimental method[83], to measure gaseous heat capacities uses an 'electric heater' element to heat the gas: the apparatus and method is inseparable from the above GH demonstrations – they are equivalent. Does this electric heater imply radiation, conduction, and, as a result of these, convection? Given the limited choices, the answer must be yes. The closest solid to share the conduction properties of air with a conduction value of 0.017 and is said to be 'extraordinary' with respect to this, is Aerogel – and is used on spacecraft for these properties.

4.8.2.1 Measurement of GHGs Specific Heat proves non-GHGs absorb IR

As it is assumed the GHGs absorb IR heat radiation in Specific Heat measurement – at their respective TE/IR and Raman modes as presented in this investigation – it is equally plausible the non-GHGs, on the same principles, are absorbing IR heat radiation at their respective Raman modes, proportional to the resulting and measured specific heat capacities. Support for this claim is found with CO_2 and CH_4 ; both are poor thermal conductors (as with 'air') and both are IR (thermoelectric) emitters. From this investigation, and based on the equipartition principle, all their modes (TE and Raman) are equivalent; therefore, this must also be the case for the non-GHGs N_2 and O_2 .

4.8.3 Vibrational Behaviour and SHC

It is interesting to read when investigating the fundamental knowledge behind the Specific Heat of matter. It is said to be determined by the vibrational behaviour of molecules, as described earlier in this investigation, including the 'degrees of freedom' that determine the specific heat capacity of a substance. This adds further weight to the

inclusion of Raman modes in radiation theory. Molecules such as N₂ and O₂ vibrate, they have degrees of freedom, and they have specific heats – so they must radiate IR also, at their Raman modes.

4.8.4 Further Paradoxes Associated with Convection – Is it all Radiation

The above work on specific heat highlights another paradox related to the transfer of heat energy: how does a gas or liquid convect without conduction or radiation? Is convection dependent on conduction and/or radiation? Is convection separate and special from the other two it is associated with?

“Convection is the heat transfer due to bulk movement of molecules within fluids such as gases and liquids. Convection takes place through advection, diffusion or both.” Wikipedia.

Further to the ‘hairdryer paradox’ presented in the introduction (figure 1), the transfer of heat energy here claimed as convection must only be by radiation. Advection and diffusion are too slow concerning the numbers (of molecules) involved, and that (again) conduction with the said gases is poor. This area needs review and further investigation.

4.9 Augmenting the Thermoelectric and Raman Atmosphere

Finally, to bring together and augment the IR-Raman modes with the TE-IR modes. Raman spectroscopy spectra, as identified and used in the Raman Exhaust Report, show the predicted N₂ and O₂ vibrational modes of these abundant molecules. These ‘Raman’ modes, along with the TE/IR modes of the EMS, can now be brought together – augmented – to complete the GHGs.

Figure 41 below is a schematic of the predicted and observed Raman vibrational modes in the Earth’s atmosphere at different electromagnetic frequencies.

Figure 41. Raman Vibrational Modes of the Atmosphere. Predicted and Raman measured vibrational modes of (some) atmospheric gases CH₄, CO₂, N₂ and O₂.

4.9.1 The Augmented Fourier Greenhouse Atmosphere spectrum

Combining thermoelectric and Raman Spectrographs (figure 42 below) reveals all the predicted and observed vibrational modes of the atmosphere. The augmented atmospheric spectrum now accounts for the hidden ‘dark’ 98% of gases in the atmosphere.

Figure 42. The Augmented Greenhouse Atmosphere. Combining Thermoelectric spectra with Raman spectra to reveal the complement of atmospheric vibrational modes and the greenhouse atmosphere of planet Earth.

In recognition of the first person to posit a 'greenhouse' atmosphere, before the advent of thermoelectrics and Raman Quantum mechanics, the augmented atmosphere may be known as the Fourier Atmosphere, where all gases are greenhouse gases.

Below (figure 43) is a diagram of the Fourier Atmosphere as read from complementary instruments, thermoelectric and Raman.

Figure 43 'IR' Thermoelectric with Raman Atmosphere. Combining the two methods of accounting for constituent gases, namely N₂, O₂, H₂O, CH₄, O₃ and more, to complete the Fourier Greenhouse Atmosphere.

Together, the IR-Raman and IR-TE modes cover all the vibrational modes of atmospheric gases, and in doing so, explain how the air absorbs and emits infrared radiation.

5 Conclusions

Without referencing any climate politics or climate records, this investigation revealed that the science of climate change is far from settled [2], and in fact, its foundations are flawed. This was a first-principles investigation to ascertain the validity of the fundamental premises and assumptions of the greenhouse effect theory: is it only the 'special "greenhouse gases that absorb and emit infrared radiation, and do the remaining non-greenhouse gases, N₂ and O₂, not? The answer was not in favour. While it is not

discussed in physics today, this assumption, as it stands, is a contradiction of quantum mechanics, which assumes that all matter above absolute zero radiates infrared radiation. In this study, a solution was found. The hypothesis of the study was clear: N₂ and O₂, at their predicted 2338 cm⁻¹ and 1556 cm⁻¹ modes respectively, both do radiate and are too GHGs, and the reason for the discrepancy lies with a misinterpretation of the fundamental greenhouse experiment – the Tyndall experiment. Tyndall only really discovered the thermoelectric gases, as measured by and as he used thermoelectric thermopile transducers. The 19th-century Tyndall experiment and the resulting greenhouse theory occurred before the advent of modern 20th-century quantum theory and the emergent technologies developed from it, specifically the modern laser-based Raman spectrometer, which complements IR spectroscopy. The investigation aimed to reconcile the contradiction by augmenting Raman spectroscopy with current ‘greenhouse theory’. To do this, the current vibrational physics and chemistry theory was reviewed, and several related real-life practical applications – that appear to contradict the status quo position – were identified.

Primarily, the investigation referred to a report in which a Raman spectrometer measured the temperature and molecular emission concentrations of N₂, O₂, and others directly from the quantum spectra of a jet engine exhaust plume. It was found from this report that N₂ and O₂’s Raman vibrational modes, and the other Raman active modes, including CO₂’s 1338 cm⁻¹ mode (which cannot be detected by thermoelectric IR spectroscopy), are equivalent (by the equipartition principle), and comply with standard quantum mechanics radiation and thermodynamics theory. N₂ and O₂ are greenhouse gases; they absorb and emit IR radiation – it is only that they are not thermoelectric. Raman instrument measurements concur with standard physical principles – including the Boltzmann constant – to the extent that they can measure temperature and gas concentration to a degree of precision equal to or greater than that of their thermoelectric counterpart. It is not the gases that are special; it is the instruments that are special. In support of this, it was found that all three of H₂O’s IR radiating modes, particularly the 3652 cm⁻¹ mode, are both – or dual–Raman and thermoelectric/IR active, which indicates that the detectors are equivalent; both can measure temperature.

As an aside, concerning IR spectroscopy, this investigation revealed that only Raman IR spectrometers radiate their samples. Thermoelectric instruments, on the other hand, transduce thermal radiation into an electromotive force (emf) and report the difference between the sample and the reference heat source. Raman instruments, it was shown, do not have the problem of emissivity, and that this is solely an infrared-thermoelectric instrument problem. It was concluded that emissivity is a limitation of the thermoelectric transducer to generate complete emf from a substance, and is not a real property of radiation. Additionally, since Raman and thermoelectric modes are equivalent, it was concluded that Raman modes, and thus N₂ and O₂, are the best ‘blackbody’ radiators, as they have an emissivity of 1. This discovery of incorporating ‘Raman modes’ into atmospheric radiation theory will challenge and possibly overturn current blackbody theory in general, where contradictions also abound, such as the assumption that water and snow are near-perfect (emissivity) absorbers.

It was also concluded that spectrographic thermoelectric infrared modes (current IR active modes) differ only, and in terms of their current part in determining the GHGs, by their possession (or not) of an electric dipole moment, and hence their respective emf

generation. All the so-called 'IR modes' – special only to the special greenhouse gases – are no more than the thermoelectric modes, and should be termed the 'thermoelectric IR modes' or TE/IR modes in short.

With knowledge of thermoelectrics and the GHGs, it should come as no coincidence – and be common sense – that the only property separating the GHGs from the non-GHGs is whether or not the gas has a mode with an electric dipole, and the electromotive force (emf) potential of this fact. One does not need to be an expert to understand that the possession of an electric dipole ('IR active') pertains directly to the thermoelectric modes that can generate electricity by thermoelectric transducers, also known as detectors. Conversely, the modes without these electric modes are the non-thermoelectric and wrongly termed 'non-GHGs'. These Tyndall gases should be referred to as thermoelectric gases (TEGs).

The CO₂ Laser was found to be a practical application in support of (solar) IR absorbing N₂ (and O₂). From the quantum mechanics behind, and the application of the CO₂ Laser, and particularly from the direct interplay between N₂ and CO₂ in it, was claimed atmospheric N₂ molecule not only absorbs (IR) photons at its 2338cm⁻¹ mode, but the energy absorbed is 'long living' metastable and is 'passed onto' the CO₂'s 2349cm⁻¹ mode. With photon absorption, it is N₂ that affects the CO₂. This finding is entirely inconsistent with the greenhouse theory; however, it has the physics and application, not to mention the real constituent volume of gas, behind it. It was shown N₂ freely absorbs at this wavenumber – outside the laboratory – and may well explain how air instantly rises in temperature – in the process of thunder production – to some 3 times the temperature of the surface of the sun – where it is said now the air 'absorbs' photons, and electrons from electron excitation – all in compliance of quantum mechanics. It was concluded that the atmosphere absorbs IR radiation from the sun by (solar) insolation directly and warms the air just as it does the oceans and the like, rather than indirectly, as it is currently assumed.

With respect to heat capacities, it was discussed that Raman and thermoelectric properties also correspond to the nominal heat capacities of the said gases.

With this new understanding of the quantum mechanics of the atmosphere – and the direct mechanics behind Raman spectroscopy – a current fallacious understanding of the 'greenhouse' atmosphere was revealed. Any extrapolation based on thermoelectric technology alone – without reference to the Seebeck effect and Raman spectroscopy – and that interprets the special GHGs alone as the IR absorbent gases, should be seen as inadmissible not only in climate and atmospheric theory, but also in any radiation theory. Climate models will need to be updated to account for the currently well-understood Raman modes and knowledge, and to conclude that all gases act as greenhouse gases, as first posited by Joseph Fourier (and possibly others) around 1828. With this new understanding, all gases comply with the 0th and 1st Laws of Thermodynamics – transferring energy towards equilibrium, where previously N₂ and O₂ were exempt.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Other Uses for Raman

8.1.1 CO₂'s 1388cm⁻¹ Excitation: The Dicke effect

Investigating whether CO₂'s 1388cm⁻¹ is excited in any way by radiation – it should not as this mode, like N₂ and O₂'s is 'Raman active' and not 'IR active' and thus, by current assumptions, should not transmit photon energy – it was found this mode is affected 'where the spectral exchange and Dicke effect play a noticeable role' [84]. The Dicke effect: 'refers to the Doppler broadening of a spectral line due to collisions the emitting species (atom or molecule) experiences with other particles' (photons) ;...the atom changes velocity and direction many times during the emission and absorption of the photon[85].

This is clear evidence this mode is active and they do radiate.

Fig. 7.21 Collision-induced absorption in the fundamental vibration band of N₂. (a) Band shape at various temperatures and (b) integrated intensity versus temperature (Thomas, Ref. 7.50).

[86]

8.1.2 Medical – anaesthetic RASCAL – Capnography Application

"In 1988 a Raman scattering instrument was introduced for clinical use. The Raman Scattering Analyzer (RASCAL)...for O₂, CO₂, N₂, N₂O; both identify and quantify these gases."
"This device is no longer marketed"[87].

These Raman devices have since advanced and are used.

"These analysers have fast response times. They can analyze multiple anesthetic agents with good accuracy (greater than infrared spectroscopy, approaching mass spectrometry)" [88].

8.1.3 Geology CO₂ 1388 cm⁻¹

In the following study: "Quantification of dissolved CO₂ in silicate glasses using micro-Raman spectroscopy" CO₂ is identified at its IR 1388 (or near about) cm⁻¹ mode.

'we propose the calibration accuracy is better than ±0.4 wt% CO₂ for our data set'[89]

8.1.4 Automobile Emission Testing.

Raman is an accepted instrument in measuring automobile emissions; it is so by exploiting the 'radiative' behaviour of the non- GHGs. This is a contradiction.

The from the USA EPA: “Raman LIDAR is self-calibrating to atmospheric oxygen and nitrogen, eliminating requirements for periodic calibration with test gases.”[90]

“The results indicate an excellent ability to identify and quantify the test species. By analyzing the sensitivity of these Phase I laboratory experiments, we estimate that the Compact UV Raman LIDAR system will be capable of achieving better than 120 parts per million (PPM) sensitivity for NO, 40 ppm for N₂ and CO, and 10 ppm for NO₂ and hydrocarbons.”

Truth be known, Raman can equally detect and quantify CO₂ (by its Raman 1388 cm⁻¹ mode) as revealed in the following study. However, before we go there, in the study ‘Rotational Raman Spectroscopy for the Remote Sensing of Carbon Dioxide’ [91] they concluded: “No Raman peaks were observed, so that the usefulness of rotational Raman for the remote sensing of CO₂ was not demonstrated.”

This maybe so for ‘remote’ solutions; however, it does not match the many results from other studies.

In the book ‘Automotive Exhaust Emission Testing.’ they acknowledged the (potential) use of Raman “Both methods (IR and Raman) are complementary” [92] pg. 128; however, it did not go onto show the use of Raman.

8.2 Understanding Raman Backscatter and the Low Wavenumbers

It has been quoted to me that these lower Lidar wavenumbers – at 580nm and 607nm respectively – are inconsistency with my theory and show N₂ and O₂ in the atmosphere do not vibrate – emit and absorb – in the IR range of the EMS as these modes or bands are in the visible range of the EMS; I have researched these lower modes and found they indeed reveal the IR modes – they need correction. The reason the Lidar wavenumbers are quoted low is because they are quoted in relation or reference to the laser frequency of the Lidar laser. They work on the ‘Raman backscatter’. When adjusted for, the differences are corrected (up) and correspond the predicted wavenumbers. This is demonstrated in the youtube presentation below[93] where in the last moments it is said: “. By using wavenumber, we see the excitation of water, independent of the excitation wavelength”.

Figure 44. Raman Lidar wavenumber discrepancy Explained. Screen shots of a Youtube presentation [93] showing how green 532nm laser light is shone (A) onto water in the case Raleigh light is revealed (B and E), but when filtered Raman red 660nm light is revealed (D and F). When this adjusted for wavenumber (cm-1) H2O's vibration band 3652cm-1 is revealed.

8.2.1 Raman Laser to Wavenumber Correction Calculation

A demonstration and method of the calculation needed to correct from the low wavelength produced by Raman Lidar and Laser to the real wavenumber vibrational bands (in this case, O₂) was found. This is evidence the often quoted low wavenumbers must be corrected or understood to be relative to the incident Raman laser frequency and not the real vibration mode.

Task: If we excite with a laser at 532 nm, where should the Stokes vibrational oxygen Raman peak appear and how strong would it be from air if the nitrogen peak is 1000 counts?

Calculate the oxygen Raman wavelength:

According to the Table the Raman shift is 1556 cm⁻¹.

With an excitation wavelength at 532 nm the oxygen Stokes line will appear at
 $1/532 \text{ nm} - 1556 \text{ cm}^{-1} = 18797 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 1556 \text{ cm}^{-1} = 17241 \text{ cm}^{-1} = 580 \text{ nm}$

Calculate the signal strength:

The signal strength of oxygen in air is one fourth of the nitrogen signal where we have to compensate for the cross section in the Table.

This means that the signal is $1000 \times \frac{1}{4} \times 1.41 = 352 \text{ counts}$

Figure 45. Scattering to Wavenumber calculation for Nitrogen. Nitrogen's 1556 cm⁻¹ predicted and observed (with Raman spectroscopy) vibration mode is corrected for the 532nm laser. [94]

8.3 Raman and Thermal Electric IR Equivalence – Dual Modes

Some modes appear to be both thermoelectric and Raman active. This indicates that although most substances do not share this (CO₂ for example); these substances must be understood to be radiating. If there is a mode; there is radiation – emission and absorption.

8.3.1 Raman Complementary to IR Thermoelectric

It is well understood by chemists Raman is a complement to 'IR' spectroscopy: no one has made brought them together with regards to the infrared atmosphere.

Raman and Infrared are Complementary Techniques

- Interestingly, although they are based on two distinct phenomena, the Raman scattering spectrum and infrared absorption spectrum for a given species often resemble one another quite closely in terms of observed frequencies.

The infrared and Raman spectrum of styrene/butadiene rubber.

Figure 46. Complementary IR and Raman Spectroscopy. Infrared above; Raman below[95]

8.3.2 H₂O is both Raman and IR (thermoelectric) Active

Water has a special property significant to vibrational mode theory, it is both Raman active and 'IR' active at: 1590 cm⁻¹, 3690cm⁻¹, and 3790cm⁻¹.

'IR' Active Thermoelectric spectra of H₂O

Figure 47. TE IR of H₂O and others.

Figure 48. Raman H_2O .

8.3.3 Other molecules with dual Raman thermoelectric.

A molecule can be characterised (and identified) based on the position and intensity of the spectral peaks by either FT/IR or Raman spectroscopy

Figure 49. [96]

Figure 50

8.3.4 Ethanol

The following is an interesting (Raman image) reference: Ethanol has both and shared Raman and thermoelectric modes. I'll drink to that.

Figure 3. Experimental vibrational spectra (Raman and IR) of liquid ethanol and assignment of the main peaks.

Figure 51. Ethanol Sharing Both Raman and Thermoelectric. [97]

Figure 52. Schematic of CO₂ Raman and IR Spectra. “In gas phase spectra of CO₂, two infrared modes are observed at 2350 and 667 cm⁻¹ (red) and a single Raman band at ~1388 cm⁻¹ (green). (The latter band is actually a doublet due to quantum mechanical resonance effects, which is beyond this discussion).” [98]

8.4 Raman spectra for Non-GHGs and GHGs

8.4.1 O₂ and N₂

Figure 53. [99]

Figure 54. Raman spectrum of air, with the oxygen and nitrogen bands marked. [100]

Figure 55. The above three images above: [101]

“It has to be noted that monoatomic gas molecules, such as nitrogen, N_2 , or oxygen, O_2 , are not affected by IR radiation and can therefore not be detected by this means. Otherwise the mentioned atmospheric greenhouse effect would be extremely severe and probably we would not exist in the current life form”. [49]

8.4.2 O_2 Spectra

Fig. 7.22 The fundamental absorption band of oxygen for a path length of 40 meters. The densities are: pure oxygen 9.59 Amagats; oxygen–nitrogen mixture, $\rho_{O_2} = 1.09$ Amagats, $\rho_{N_2} = 56$ Amagats; oxygen–argon mixture, $\rho_{O_2} = 1.12$ Amagats, $\rho_{Ar} = 57.9$ Amagats (Shapiro and Gush, Ref. 7.62, with permission). (Note: 1 Amagat is the STP ratio of pressure in atm to temperature in K.)

Figure 56. [86]

8.4.3 N₂ 2338 cm⁻¹

Fig. 12.11. The rotational-vibrational Raman spectrum of the nitrogen molecule, $^{14}N_2$. In the centre, at the position of the vibrational wavenumber $\bar{\nu}_e = 2330 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, the Q branch ($\Delta J = 0$) appears as a broad line. In $^{14}N_2$, with $I = 1$, an alternating intensity of the rotational lines with a ratio 1:2 is observed. After Hellwege

Figure 57. Raman peaks of N₂ at the predicted 2330cm-1 – page 209 [102]

8.4.4 O₂ 1556

Figures 6 and 7 below show Raman spectrograph peaks of N₂ at O₂ at the predicted 1556cm-1 and 2330cm-1 (pages 205 and 209 respectively) both within the infrared range of the electromagnetic spectrum.

Fig. 12.7. A section of the rotational-vibrational Raman spectrum of oxygen, $^{16}\text{O}_2$. This is a vibrational line (Stokes line) with its accompanying rotational lines. In the centre, at the energy of the vibrational wavenumber $\bar{\nu}_e = 1556 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, we see the Q branch ($\Delta J = 0$) as a broad line. For $^{16}\text{O}_2$ ($I = 0$), the lines with even J are missing; cf. Sect. 12.4. After Hellwege

Figure 58. Raman peak of O_2 at the predicted 1556cm^{-1} [102] – page 205.

8.4.5 CH_4

Figure 59. Synthesis in LH DAC at 48 GPa. Black line shows CH_4 Raman spectrum before heating. Blue line shows Raman spectrum collected at $1,445 \text{ K}$ with evident CH_4 dissociation. Red line shows Raman spectrum of reaction products collected after heating to $2,000 \text{ K}$. The labels near the curves suggest the assignment of the Raman bands. HP modes of CH_4 refer to vibrations caused by partial orientational ordering of methane HP phase. Panels a–c show different parts of the spectral range.[103]

Figure 60. IR (top curve) and Raman spectra of the mixture H₂O:CH₄:N₂ before (curve a) and after (curves b and c, corresponding to doses of 378 eV/16 amu and 825 eV/16 amu respectively) irradiation with He⁺ (30 keV) ions at low temperature (12 K). In spectra b and c the ice features are undetectable because of the intense fluorescence background. The arrow in the IR spectrum indicates the position of the N≡N symmetric stretching mode, which cannot be observed. Fig. 3 [104].

8.4.6 H₂

Hydrogen gas is assumed a non-GHG as it has similar properties to the other non-GHGs; however, it is predicted at 4342cm⁻¹ (table 2) and observed by Raman spectrometers as below figure 65.

Figure 2. Raman spectrum of 1% H₂ in CH₄. The sharp bands below 1040cm⁻¹ are the pure rotational transitions of the H₂ molecule.

Figure 61. CH₄, H₂, with N₂ Raman Spectra. [105]

8.4.7 H₂O Raman

Earth atmospheric temperatures are too warm for H₂O's Raman signatures too show. The predicted vibrational modes are shown below.

KOLESOV: RAMAN INVESTIGATION OF H₂O MOLECULES IN HEMIMORPHITE

1359

FIGURE 5. Temperature evolution of the polarized spectra showing the O-H and H₂O stretching modes in hemimorphite; (a) *aa*-spectra and (b) *cc*-spectra. The appearance of the new band at around 3500 cm⁻¹ at $T \geq 100$ K is shown by the arrow.

Figure 62. [106]

8.4.8 H₂O TE IR

NIST Chemistry WebBook (<http://webbook.nist.gov/chemistry>)

Figure 63. H2O IR Spectra Showing 3652cm Band.

8.4.9

8.4.10 Ge Germanium

Figure 1: Raman spectra of diamond, crystalline silicon, and crystalline germanium

Figure 1: Raman spectra of diamond, crystalline silicon, and crystalline germanium.

Figure 64. [107],[108]

Figure 2. A typical Raman spectrum measured at the site in this study. Key peaks: H₂O vapor (3657cm⁻¹), N₂ (2331cm⁻¹), O₂ (1555cm⁻¹), and CO₂ (Fermi dyad at 1388 and 1285cm⁻¹).

Figure 65. Raman Spectra of N₂, O₂, CO₂ and H₂O together. [109]

8.5 The following text is a (typical) chemistry explanation as to why N₂ and O₂ are not GHG's [110]:

"N₂ and O₂ have no dipole, so they are not greenhouse gases. Nitrogen (N₂) is symmetrical AND made of identical atoms. Even with rotation or vibration, there is no unequal sharing of electrons between one N atom and the other. So N₂ has no dipole, and an EM photon passes by without being absorbed. Similarly, for O₂."

8.5.1 Greenhouse and Non-greenhouse (thermoelectric and non-thermoelectric) wavenumbers

In detail, from the table (1), each molecule has a specific (calculated) number of modes (degrees of freedom): N₂ and O₂ have 1 each, at 2331 cm⁻¹ and 1556 cm⁻¹ respectively. CO₂ has 3 degrees of freedom – 2 IR thermoelectric (at 2349 cm⁻¹ and 667 cm⁻¹) and 1 non-thermoelectric (at 1338 cm⁻¹); CH₄ has 6 degrees of freedom: 4 thermoelectric and 2 non-thermoelectric; and H₂O has 3 degrees of freedom – 2 thermoelectric (at 1595cm⁻¹ and 3756cm⁻¹), and 1 non-thermoelectric (at 3652cm⁻¹).

8.5.2 Mode Type, Thermoelectric or Raman,

The mode type (shown in column 4 table 1) is to me the crux of the greenhouse problem: greenhouse theory posits it is these mode-types that specifically determine what is, or what is not a greenhouse gas. It also assumes the non-thermoelectric modes do not 'thermally radiate. This cannot be true. I argue there has been a misconception: the non-thermoelectric modes have been ignored and discriminated, but if they are real, they are there (as we shall soon see) and they do radiate.

8.5.3 Electric Dipole Moments

If a molecule has a vibration mode other than a symmetric mode it possesses an electric dipole moment. This electric dipole moment is a key word here: if an electric dipole moves, it generates electricity (with thermo-electric transducers); if not, they do not. As can be seen, the thermoelectric (IR active/ greenhouse gas) modes of all the gases have all types of modes (**stretch, wag, and so on**). It is the non-greenhouse gases that have symmetric modes. Symmetric directly implies – to be clear – no electric dipole: no electricity generated by the thermo-electric transducers, and it is for this reason they do not show up – at any temperature. This where the problem lies; and this is where it ends.

If a molecule has only one of these electric (dipole) modes, it is enough to call it a greenhouse gas. N₂ and O₂ have no electric dipole modes and so are (correctly) not detected, but incorrectly termed non-greenhouse gases as this does not mean they are not radiating. CO₂ also has one electric dipole mode that are also missing from this IR spectrograph, and CH₄ two.

To reiterate: if a mode or gas possesses an electric dipole moment (or movement) – revealed simply from a movement of the dipole – it is a greenhouse gas. These modes will show on a spectrograph like **figure** above.

8.6 Thermal Image with Raman

Find the thermal image and write it up.

(a) Raman image of 2D-mode peak position before self-heating. Variation in peak position indicative of multilayer boundaries and mobility reductions are evident near left contact. (b) IR measured temperature distribution while dissipating 325 mW of power. (c) Raman image of 2D-mode peak position after failure. (d) Overlay of (b,c) indicating that the failure is co-located with regions of most severe heating. The grounded electrode is on the right-hand side.

Figure 66. [111]

8.7 Raman LIDAR and the Atmosphere

While I have shown N₂ and O₂ both have vibration modes that satisfy the prediction made of them (2330 and 1556cm⁻¹ respectively) different and lower wavenumber observations

of them are made by using Lidar.

Fig. 3 (a) Altitude-dependent atmospheric N₂ Stokes vibrational-rotational Raman spectra derived from the spectrally resolved Raman lidar measurement at Wuhan during 0000-0100 LT on 12 May 2013. (b) Signal intensity profiles for the 16th (Q branch; magenta), 24th (S branch, $J = 6$; red) and 30th (S branch, $J = 12$; blue) channels, respectively.

Figure 67. Diagram showing N₂ by Lidar, altitude and wavenumber, more evidence to N₂ 2349cm-1 vibration mode. [112]

In the diagram below N₂, O₂, and H₂O are shown with their Raman scatter wavelength – 580, 607, and 660nm from the incident laser 532nm a line with the their respective wavenumbers, 1553, 2330, and 3652 cm⁻¹.

Figure 68. 112]

Lidar can reveal the temperature of the atmosphere:

“The RL measures atmospheric temperature using the ratio of two signals from the lidar’s rotational Raman (RR) channels. The RR channels sense Raman-shifted backscatter arising from rotational energy state transitions in atmospheric N₂ and O₂ molecules due to excitation at the laser wavelength of 354.7 nm (Di Girolamo et al. 2004, Behrendt et al. 2004, Radlach et al. 2008).” [114].

6.0 Example Plots

Figure 4. Sample output from the RLPROFTEMP VAP covering four selected months. Results are shown for (a) January 2009, (b) April 2009, (c) July 2009, and (d) October 2009.

Figure 69. [114]

Figure 70. [115]

In another example, Raman uses methane and Nitrogen to measure temperature.

“An airborne lidar to measure methane, water vapor, and temperature on board NASA’s flying laboratory, the DC-8, has been developed at Goddard Space Flight Center. Methane and water are measured using Raman (inelastic) scattering, while temperatures are determined from both Rayleigh (elastic) scattering and nitrogen Raman. Methane’s long stratospheric lifetime (approximately a decade) makes it an ideal conserved tracer to track the motions of streamers or filaments of air as they peel off the polar vortex.

Temperature measurements allow a calculation of the quasi-conserved quantity, potential temperature, which is useful in following the motions of large air parcels. The water measurement allows stratospheric water transport across the subtropical boundary to be studied.” [115] “ Page 273”

Figure 71. Atmospheric N₂ by Raman Lidar at laser stimulation 354.8nm. Notice the wavenumber of 2330cm⁻¹ is shown and also temperature is deduced. [112]

8.8 Animals that can see IR

Humans do not see the infrared, but some other animals can – pit snakes are the best example. These snakes have pits that house ‘detectors’ and their vision is said to be just or much like a thermal camera – at least that is how it is described by experts. If this is so, then the question is: are they are exploiting thermoelectricity and the Seebeck effect? I have found no reference to this; but, they seem to be able to see animal heat, but not - interestingly – the temperature of the air. My question here is whether snakes – like us with our thermopiles – see all the IR? No, they do not – they see only the thermoelectric as far as one can tell. It appears they are as limited – or discriminant – as we are. They, like us, are exploiting a property of substances – thermoelectricity.

Some tests that may clear things would be: can the snake see 'hot' objects through glass? The thermal camera cannot and a no answer to this would suggest they are thermoelectric. The hypothesis they are.

It is interesting that fish – for the most part – cannot detect IR or use it directly: this makes seen as water is a thermoelectric substance. The question that would be interesting